

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSES OF
REPRESENTATIVE REGIONS**

(BASELINE STUDY)

**THE CASE OF SANTO ANTAO AND MAIO ISLANDS OF CAPE
VERDE**

Final Report

**(Appendix C of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env.
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	VII
ABBREVIATIONS	IX
CHAPTER 1	10
BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES	10
1.1 The CIRAWA Project	10
1.2 Study Area	11
1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)	12
1.4 Methodology (Brief on Sampling and Data Collecting and Analysis-Summary).....	12
CHAPTER 2	13
SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS	13
2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members	13
2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses	18
2.3 Farm Sizes and Types	20
2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes	20
2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming	22
2.3.3 Land preparation methods.....	24
2.3.4 Numbers of farm plots and their locations	25
2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming	26
2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots	26
2.4.2 Use of inorganic and organic fertilizers by men and women farmers	28
CHAPTER 3	30
FARMING SYSTEMS IN THE ISLANDS	30
3.1 Crop-Based Systems	30
3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures	30
3.1.2 Planting materials and sources	33
3.1.3 Soil amendment practices.....	34
3.1.4 Crop production constraints.....	35
3.2 Livestock-Based Systems.....	38
3.2.1 Animal ownership and management.....	38
3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics.....	40
3.2.3 Livestock constraints	45
3.3 Irrigated Farming Systems	51
3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated and soil amendments.....	51

3.3.2 Soil amendments in irrigated plots and perceived success of irrigation.....	52
3.3.2 Irrigation constraints.....	53
CHAPTER 4.....	54
OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS.....	54
4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources.....	54
4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale.....	54
4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources.....	56
4.2 Expenditure by Households.....	59
CHAPTER 5.....	61
HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY, DIETARY DIVERSITY AND WEALTH AND POVERTY PERCEPTIONS.....	61
5.1 Household Food Security.....	61
5.1.1 Shortages of cultivated crops by months in 2021 and 2022.....	61
5.1.2 Sources of income for food purchases.....	62
5.2 Household Dietary Diversity.....	63
5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day- HHH.....	63
5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHH.....	64
5.2.3 Household heads and women in household comparison in Santo Antao Island.....	66
5.3 Wealth and Poverty Status of Households and Communities (To be completed).....	66
CHAPTER 6.....	67
HOUSEHOLD RESOURCE AND USE.....	67
6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time.....	67
6.2 Reasons for Yields Change Over Time.....	68
CHAPTER 7.....	71
AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES.....	71
7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices.....	71
7.1.1 Agroecological awareness and practices in Santo Antao Island.....	71
7.1.2 Agroecological awareness and practices in Maio Island.....	73
7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices.....	74
7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes and Their Uses in Santo Antao and Maio Islands.....	77
CHAPTER 8.....	80
CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES.....	80
8.1 Evidence of Climate Change.....	80
CHAPTER 9.....	81
SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	81

9.1 Summary	81
9.2 Recommendations	81
APPENDICES	83

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken.....	12
Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in Santo Antao and Maio	13
Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in Santo Antao and Maio	14
Table 2.3: Average ages of household heads (HHHs) and spouses.....	14
Table 2.4: Crop farming experiences of HHHs.....	15
Table 2.5: Length of time household heads have been in the Islands	15
Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs	15
Table 2.7 Household size distributions (Std. Dev. are in parentheses)	16
Table 2.8 HH members contributions to farming and other activities – Santo Antao	18
Table 2.9: HH members contributions to farming and other activities – Maio	18
Table 2.10: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses – Santo Antao	19
Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and Spouses - Maio	19
Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in m2) – Men (HHH) respondents	20
Table 2.13: Household and individual farm sizes (in m2) – Women (WiHH) respondents.....	21
Table 2.14: Methods of land acquisition for farming according to men (HHH).....	23
Table 2.15: Methods of land acquisition for farming according to women (WiHH) – Santo Antao	24
Table 2.16: Land preparation methods.....	24
Table 2.17: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms - Santo Antao (HHH)..	25
Table 2.18: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms - Maio (HHH).....	25
Table 2.19: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms – Santo Antao (WiHH)	26
Table 2.20: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots by men (HHH)	27
Table 2.21: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots by women (WiHH).....	27
Table 2.22: Inorganic fertilizer utilization by men farmers (HHH).....	28
Table 2.23: Inorganic fertilizer utilization by women in Santo Antao (WiHH).....	28
Table 2.24: Organic fertilizer utilization by men in Santo Antao and Maio (HHH).....	29
Table 2.25: Organic fertilizer utilization by women in Santo Antao (WiHH)	29
Table 3.1: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in Santo Antao	30
Table 3.2: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in Maio	31
Table 3.3: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in women headed households (HHH) in Santo Antao	32
Table 3.4: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Santo Antao	32
Table 3.5: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Maio	33
Table 3.6: Types and sources of planting materials- Santo Antao HHH.....	33
Table 3.7: Types and sources of planting materials- Maio HHH.....	34
Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- Santo Antao WiHH.....	34
Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH	35
Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH	35
Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Santo Antao Island for the years 2022 and 2023	38
Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Santo Antao Island for the years 2022 and 2023	39

Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Maio island for the years 2022 and 2023 .	40
Tables 3.14: Livestock breeds reared by men in Santo Antao and Maio islands	41
Table 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by women in Santo Antao	41
Table 3.16 Men and women sources of animal breeds in Santo Antao	42
Table 3.17 Men main source of animal breeds in Maio	43
Table 3.18: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in Santo Antao Island	44
Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads in Maio island	45
Table 3.20: Types of irrigation undertaken	51
Table 3.21: Types of crops grown under irrigation	51
Table 3.22: Types of soil amendments used in irrigated plots.	52
Tables 3.23: Perceived degree of success of irrigation in islands	52
Table 3.24: Irrigation constraints	53
Table 4.1: Method of estimation of household income of harvested crops	54
Table 4.2: Value of crop output per household*	55
Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold according men and women in Santo Antao and Maio	56
Table 4.4: Non-farm income (Cape Verde Escudo - CVE) of HHHs (men) and WiHH (women) – Santo Antao and Maio (1 Euro = 102.04 CVE)	57
Table 4.5: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023) – HHH.....	59
Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022	61
Table 5.2: Sources of income for food purchase.....	62
Table 5.3: Household head Dietary Diversity (HDDS) Cape Verde	64
Table 5.4 Women in household Dietary Diversity (WiHDDS) Cape Verde	65
Table 6.1: Availability and use of household lands in Santo Antao and Maio Islands	67
Table 6.2: Availability of additional land for farming	68
Table 6.3: Source of extra land for farming in Santo Antao and Maio	68
Table 7.1: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Santo Antao Island	72
Table 7.2: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Santo Antao Island.....	73
Table 7.3: HHHs agroecological technologies in Maio Island	74
Tables 7.4: Factors determining use of agroecological practices by men and women in Santo Antao	75
Tables 7.5: Factors determining use of agroecological practices by men and women in Santo Antao	75
Tables 7.6: Factors determining use of agroecological practices by men in Maio island.....	76
Tables 7.7: Factors determining use of agroecological practices by men in Maio island.....	76
Table 7.8A Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Santo Antao Island (N = 25).....	77
Table 7.8B Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Santo Antao Island (N = 25) (Continued)	78
Table 7.9A Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Santo Antao Island (N = 17).....	78
Table 7.9B Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Santo Antao Island (N = 17) (Continued)	79

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution.....	17
Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH) and individual men farm sizes (Santo Antao and Maio)	21
Figure 2.3: Distribution of household (HH) and individual women farm sizes (according to WiHHs – Santo Antao)	22
Figure 2.4: Methods of land acquisition (according to HHHs)	23
Figure 3.1: Household heads (men) crop production constraints by Island	36
Figure 3.2 WiHH crop production constraints – Santo Antao	37
Figure 3.3: Household head cattle production constraints by island	46
Figure 3.4: Household head (men) goat production constraints by island	47
Figure 3.5: Women goat production constraints in Santo Antao	47
Figure 3.6: Household head sheep production constraints by island.....	48
Figure 3.7 Household head pig production constraints by island.....	49
Figure 3.8 Women in household pig production constraints in Santo Antao Island.....	49
Figure 3.9 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by island.....	50
Figure 3.10 Women fowl (chicken) production constraints Santo Antao Island	50
Figure 4.1: Relative importance of non-farm sources according to HHHs - Santo Antao and Maio.....	58
Figure 4.2: Relative importance of non-farm income sources according to WiHHs – Santo Antao	58
Figure 4.3: Relative importance of HH expenditure items	60
Figure 6.1: Household heads reasons for increase in yields over time by in Santo Antao	69
Figure 6.2 WiHH reasons for increase in yields over time – Santo Antao	69
Figure 6.3 HHHs reasons for decrease in yields over time by island	70
Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields over time in Santo Antao.....	70

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Estimation of household income from harvested crops	83
Appendix 2: Computation of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies.....	83
Appendix 3 - Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies – Household head expenditure in 12 months	85

ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CV	Cape Verde
CVE	Cape Verde Escudo
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
GD	Green Deal
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HHH	Household Head
KIIs	Key Informant Interviews
WiHH	Women in Household Head
WP	Work Package

CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

1.1 The CIRAWA Project

CIRAWA – Agroecological Strategies for Resilient Farming in West Africa, is an EU-funded project, which aims to “unlock the potential of agroecology in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling the climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices”. CIRAWA is working on innovative agroecological approaches using among others, the following strategies:

- 1) valorisation of agro-wastes and bio-based fertiliser production;
- 2) production of high-quality seeds;
- 3) saline soil reclamation through phytoremediation; and
- 4) soil fertility, water and crop management practices.

These strategies are being deployed in 4 countries in West Africa: Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal and The Gambia.

The CIRAWA Project (and three similar ones in North, East and Central Africa) arose out of the EU-AU collaborative efforts in agriculture and the focus of the EU to facilitate a green transition according to its Green Deal (GD) objectives, which basically define the EU’s climate strategy to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It is also in line with the EU-Africa biodiversity strategy which seeks to create a circular economy.

Even though the original proposal indicated that certain specific activities will be undertaken in the different countries, it has been pointed out and agreed that almost all the proposed intervention activities are required in all the countries. Thus, the following activities are expected to be undertaken in the various countries in consultation with farmers with regards to their needs and requirements.

- 1) Characterisation of local soils: fertility studies.
- 2) Characterisation of locally available manures and crop-residues, protocol definition and implementation and production of innovative vermi-compost and bio-based fertilisers.
- 3) Characterisation of locally available crop-residues and production of materials for household energy production.
- 4) Soil conservation practices.
- 5) Saline soil reclamation strategies through an integrated approach based on salt-tolerant species (phytoremediation).
- 6) Crop management decision support system: irrigation and fertilisation modules.
- 7) High quality seeds production and multiplication, with consideration given to characterization and improvements of seeds of indigenous crops.

- 8) Water collection techniques: cloud/fog harvesting, which is particularly important for Cape Verde.
- 9) Strategies to increase access of farmers to markets.
- 10) Awareness creation campaigns to promote agro-ecological farming system.
- 11) Farming system cross-border best-practices integration platform.
- 12) Promoting participatory and inclusive governance, especially for women and youth.

In Cape Verde, the islands of Santo Antao and Maio were chosen for the implementation of the CIRAWA project.

1.2 Study Area

Cape Verde (or the Republic of Cabo Verde) is a Portuguese-speaking African country consisting of 10 islands (and 8 islets) situated in the Atlantic Ocean, about 570 kilometers off the coast of the mainland West Africa. Close neighbours include Senegal, The Gambia, and Guinea Bissau. It lies between latitudes 14 and 18 degrees N and longitudes 22 and 26 degrees W. It has a combined area of 4,033 square kilometers and a population of about half a million people (483,628 according to the 2021 census). Its capital is Praia situated on the island of Santiago. About 65% of the people of Cape Verde live in urban settings and over 90% of the food of the country is imported. Agriculture and fishing contribute less than 10% of the GDP. The country's economy is dominated by the tertiary sector, led by tourism. It is a leader in the use of renewable energy in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA); about 20% of its energy is from renewable energy sources. It is the headquarters of the ECOWAS Regional Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency.

These two islands, in which the CIRAWA project is being carried out, Santo Antao and Maio, have significant contrasting characteristics. Santo Antao, the third largest island in Cape Verde, has a population of 36,362 (2021 population census) and Maio has a population of only 6,296 (2021 census). Santo Antao belongs to the Barlavento (windward) group of islands, while Maio belongs to the Sotavento (leeward) group of islands. Santo Antao is a very mountainous, rocky and relatively wet island with considerable vegetation and forests, while Maio is relatively flat, sandy, and arid with only about 2% of the land being arable. Santo Antao has a diversified vegetation consisting of subtropical, tropical and endemic plant species composing a unique biodiversity. Many parts of the island have abundant water and fertile soils for growing crops such as maize, banana and sugarcane but the south is arid with herbaceous vegetation. The high zones of Santo Antao are covered with trees like the eucalyptus, the cypress, and the pine-tree. Maio on the other hand has a desert-like vegetation. The Island is dominated by shrubs and low-lying plants such as acacia, cacti and succulent. Crops grown in the limited arable areas of Maio include maize, beans and fruits. The city of Porto Novo is the capital of Santo Antao while Vila do Maio is the capital of Maio.

The selection of contrasting areas is important so that diversity in the social, economic, environmental, and other activities and situations can be obtained from the different islands. The contrasting situations will also provide wider experiences of what agroecological practices

and strategies are possible in those islands. That will have significant implications and possible applications in the other islands of Cape Verde and possibly in other West African countries. Cross-learning and trial of practices across different environments are useful forms of co-creation, co-discovery and co-innovations.

1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)

The overall objective of WP2 is for qualitative and quantitative assessment of farmers’ and communities’ needs and requirements, and their resource availability and use as well as identification of the available agroecological practices taking place in the different locations and how they are adapted to local needs and contexts. It also provides baseline information on social, economic and environmental indicators against which project progress and effectiveness during implementation can be monitored and evaluated.

1.4 Methodology (Brief on Sampling and Data Collecting and Analysis-Summary)

Qualitative and quantitative research designs were used in the information and data collection from various people in the two islands. Focus group discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs) were used to collect most of the qualitative information while in-depth household interviews were used to collect most of the quantitative information. Data collection protocols were designed and used to solicit information from farmers and other stakeholders on farmers’ requirements and needs as part of the socio-economic and environmental baseline survey. It involved the use of enumerators and supervisors who are conversant with the different environments and the languages spoken by the people. They, however, had to be trained in the data collection process so that they could interact effectively to tease out the important requirements and needs of farmers and community members. WACWISA-UDS team together with other CIRAWA Partners at the country level trained the supervisors and enumerators and took part in some of the field activities.

Table 1.1 shows the numbers of communities and households sampled from the two islands. Both men and women were interviewed in some of the households in Santo Antao. It was not possible to interview women in Maio due to some constraints.

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken

Island	Number of Focus Group Discussions	Number of Key informant Interviews	Household interviews	
			Men	Women
Santo Antao	4	5	26	17
Maio	3	4	15	0
Total	7	9	41	17

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

CHAPTER 2

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS

2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members

In Santo Antao, the HHH (men) questionnaire was administered to mainly men headed households and the WiHH (women) questionnaire was administered to mainly women headed households. That is why the men reported that about 88% of those interviewed were men headed households while the women reported that 94.1% of households sampled for interview were women headed households (Table 2.1). The inference from Table 2.1 is that there are almost equal numbers of men and women headed households in Santo Antao. The situation in Santo Antao contrasts very significantly with other West African countries where very few women are household heads.

In Maio however, the questionnaire (HHH questionnaire) was administered to only men. It was difficult to get women respondents. It is however interesting to note that the men interviewed in Maio indicated that 2 households (13.3%) were women headed households. It is hoped that the CIRAWA Project will be able to actively involve women so that by the end of the project some level of women empowerment will be obvious.

Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in Santo Antao and Maio

Island	As reported by Men (through HHH questionnaire)				As reported by Women (through the WiHH questionnaire)			
	Men headed households		Women headed households		Men headed households		Women headed households	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	23	88.5	3	11.5	1	5.9	16	94.1
Maio	13	86.7	2	13.3	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

As given in Table 2.2, 84.6% of the men farmers interviewed in Santo Antao are indigenes, and 15.4% are non-indigenes. For the women farmers of Santo Antao, 88.2% of them are indigenes and only 11.8% non-indigenes (Table 2.2). In the case of Maio all the households sampled are indigenes. That is very much expected given the remoteness of the island of Maio and the inter-island transportation difficulties of Cape Verde.

Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in Santo Antao and Maio

Island	Men headed households				Women headed households			
	Indigenes		Non-indigenes		Indigenes		Non-indigenes	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	22	84.6	4	15.4	15	88.2	2	11.8
Maio	15	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total (both Islands)	37	84.6	4	15.4	15	88.2	2	11.8

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

The average ages of the men respondents (household heads) in Santo Antao and Maio are 46.2 years and 51.4 years respectively with relatively low standard deviations as shown in Table 2.3. The corresponding average ages of their spouses are 46.4 years and 46.0 years respectively. Since household heads (HHHs) are usually the oldest in the HHHs, the indication is that the farming population in the islands is relatively youthful. Other factors remaining constant, a youthful population is likely to be more eager to try new ideas and adopt progressive technologies and especially technologies that build on their indigenous knowledge.

Table 2.4 indicates that the farmers in the two islands have considerable farming experience. A comparison of Tables 2.3 and 2.4 indicates that the household heads have been farmers for most of their adult lives.

Table 2.3: Average ages of household heads (HHHs) and spouses

Island	Ages of HHHs			Ages of spouses of HHHs		
	Mean (Std Dev)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean (Std Dev)	Minimum	Maximum
Santo Antao	46.2 (11.99)	25	67	46.4 (28.17)	24	93
Maio	51.4 (10.97)	32	74	46.0 (11.83)	35	65
Total (both Islands)	48.8 (11.48)	25	74	46.2 (20.00)	24	93

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.4: Crop farming experiences of HHHs

Islands	Crop farming experience (HHHs)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Santo Antao	27.1	14.93	5	60
Maio	26.9	15.25	7	60
Total (both Islands)	27.0	15.09	5	60

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 2.5 shows that over 90% of the farmers have been in their present locations for over 20 years in both Santo Antao and Maio islands. It implies that both men and women respondents are very conversant with the farming history as well as the agricultural production and livelihood dynamics of the area.

Table 2.5: Length of time household heads have been in the Islands

Years in Island	< 5 years		5 – 10 years		11 – 20 years		> 20 years	
Island	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.3	22	95.7
Maio	1	9.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	10	90.9

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

With respect to formal educational status Table 2.6 indicates that the HHHs in Santo Antao are more educated than their counterparts in Maio. About 76.2% of the respondents in Maio had only primary school education. That compares to 45.5% and 45.4% of the respondents that had primary school and post-primary education respectively in Santo Antao. It is worth noting that none of the respondents in the islands had tertiary level education.

Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs

	Santo Antao		Maio	
	HHHs		HHHs	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Pre-School	-	-	-	-
Primary	15	45.5	16	76.2
JHS/MSLC	7	21.2	-	-
SHS/Technical /O&A-Levels	8	24.2	5	23.8
Tertiary	-	-	-	-
None (no form of classroom instructions)	3	9.1	-	-
Total	33	100.0	21	100.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Household (HH) size distributions in the islands are as presented in Table 2.7 and Figure 2.1. The average household size in Santo Antao is 4.8 (with a very low standard deviation of 0.57) and that of Maio is much higher, 6.8 with a standard deviation of 1.02. This implies that the largest HH size in Santo Antao and Maio will be about 6 and 8 persons respectively. These figures are expected since more remote areas tend to have larger household sizes. The composition of the household sizes gives some indication of the relative availability of labour for farming activities. As the table and figure indicate, there are more male and female adults per household in Maio than in Santo Antao, thus the scarcity of labour is likely to be a bigger problem in Santo Antao than in Maio.

Table 2.7 Household size distributions (Std. Dev. are in parentheses)

Island		Male adults	Female adults	Male children	Female children	Total HH size
Santo Antao	Average	1.2	0.9	1.4	1.3	4.8
	Std. Dev.	0.75	0.28	0.62	0.48	0.57
	Max.	2	1	3	2	-
	Min.	0	0	1	1	-
Maio	Average	2.0	1.8	1.3	1.8	6.8
	Std. Dev.	1.73	1.33	0.46	0.96	1.02
	Max.	4	4	2	3	-
	Min.	1	1	1	1	-
Total (both Islands)	Average	1.6	1.38	1.31	1.5	5.8
	Std. Dev.	1.24	0.80	0.54	0.719	0.79
	Max.	4	4	3	3	-
	Min.	0	0	1	1	-

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution

Information was sought on the contributions of different HH members to HH farming and other activities. That information is given in Table 2.8 and 2.9 for Santo Antao and Maio respectively. Table 2.8 and 2.9 indicate that male adults and male children are those who prepare farmlands in Santo Antao but male adults and female adults tend to be those in charge of land preparation in Maio. Also planting, weeding and harvesting are carried out by male and female adults as well as male children in Santo Antao but in Maio children do not take part in such tasks.

Children are however involved in feeding and shepherding livestock, carrying water, running errands and undertaking household chores. It is noteworthy that all categories of household members are involved in the harvesting of crops in Santo Antao but in Maio, male adults and male children tend not to be involved in crop harvesting. It could be interesting to find out why. It is however necessary to recognize the limitations of the information obtain since the sample sizes used were relatively small.

Table 2.8 HH members contributions to farming and other activities – Santo Antao

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	3	75.0	0	0.0	1	25.0	0	0.0	4
Planting	2	28.6	3	42.9	2	28.6	0	0.0	7
Weeding	2	25.0	4	50.0	2	25.0	0	0.0	8
Harvesting	2	13.3	8	53.3	3	20.0	2	13.3	15
Feeding animals	2	25.0	3	37.5	3	37.5	0	0.0	8
Shepherding livestock	3	30.0	2	20.0	4	40.0	1	10.0	10
Errands	0	0.0	3	42.9	3	42.9	1	14.3	7
HH Chores	1	8.3	8	66.7	1	8.3	2	16.7	12
Carrying water	1	33.3	0	0.0	1	33.3	1	33.3	3
Carrying firewood	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1
Irrigation	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	1

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.9: HH members contributions to farming and other activities – Maio

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2
Planting	1	33.3	2	66.7	0	0.0	0	0.0	3
Weeding	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2
Harvesting	0	0.0	2	66.7	0	0.0	1	33.3	3
Feeding animals	0	0.0	2	50.0	1	25.0	1	25.0	3
Shepherding livestock	0	0.0	1	33.3	2	66.7	0	0.0	3
Errands	1	16.7	2	33.3	2	33.3	1	16.7	6
HH chores	0	0.0	3	100.0	0	0.00	0	0.0	3
Carrying water	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	1

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses

The main occupations of HHHs in Santo Antao are arable crop farming (68%) and livestock farming (24%). Arable cropping and livestock are also the minor occupations of some HHHs (30.4% and 43.5% respectively) (Table 2.10). It shows the very dominant role of crop and livestock farming in Santo Antao. Fishing and crop produce marketing among others are also some of their minor occupations. Responses for the spouses in both islands were too few

for reasonable inferences to be made (see Table 2.10 and 2.11). However, during focus group discussions, arable crop and livestock production were identified as the main economic activities by the women of Casa do Meio in Santo Antao Island. The women however pointed out that agricultural activities in Casa do Meio are carried out by mainly the men. Most of them, the women, are “housewives”. It was also pointed out during FGDs that main economic activity of the inhabitants of Chã de Feijoal (Santo Antao) is livestock rearing and poultry production (for milk and cheese, meat and eggs, and manure). They, in addition cultivate small arable crop plots (< 1000m²). Women are very much involved in the livestock rearing and undertake produce (crop and livestock) marketing. This is indication that interventions aimed at improving crop and livestock productivity and sustainability will be very welcome by both men and women in the islands.

Table 2.10: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses – Santo Antao

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)*	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	17 (68.0)	7 (30.4)	1 (16.7)	2 (100)
Livestock farming	6 (24.0)	10 (43.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Fishing	0 (0.0)	1 (4.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Produce marketing (crop)	0 (0.0)	2 (8.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Tree produces processing (e.g. shea, dawadawa, baobab, etc.)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Petty trading/food vending	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Salaried worker	0 (0.0)	1 (4.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Others	2 (8.0)	2 (8.7)	5 (83.3)	0 (0.0)
Total	25 (100.0)	23 (100.0)	6 (100)	2 (100.0)

Source: Field Survey, May 2023 *The responses for the spouses are too few for inferences to be drawn.

Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and Spouses - Maio

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)*	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	6 (85.7)	1 (16.7)	0(0.0)	0 (0.0)
Livestock farming	0 (0.0)	3 (50.0)	1(50.0)	0 (0.0)
Produce marketing (Crop)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (50.0)	0 (0.0)
Tree produces processing (e.g. shea, dawadawa, baobab etc.)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Others	7 (14.3)	2 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Total	13 (100.0)	6 (100.0)	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)

Source: Field Survey, May 2023*The responses for the spouses are too few for inferences to be drawn

2.3 Farm Sizes and Types

2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes

Farmland scarcity is a critical problem in all islands across the globe and so it is in Cape Verde. Areas cultivated are thus very small (compared to mainland West Africa). The farm plots have been estimated in square meters (m²) (1 acre =4046.86 m²). Table 2.12 and Figure 2.2 give the average areas obtained from men farmers (HHHs) in Santo Antao and Maio while Table 2.13 and Figure 2.3 are the average areas obtained from women farmers (WiHHs) in Santo Antao. There is a considerable difference between the system of crop farming in the two islands. In Santo Antao the average area of “individual men farms” is double that of the “household farm” (Table 2.12 and Figure 2.2) according to the men respondents. That means there is a greater emphasis on individual farms as against household farms. In contrast, there are no “individual farms” in Maio. All the farms are household farms. It is also noteworthy that in both islands there are no “individual women farms” in men-headed households (Table 2.12). In women-headed households in Santo Antao the “individual women farms” are also far larger than the household farms and there are no individual men farms (Table 2.13 and Figure 2.3). In terms of the sizes of the farm plots, average household farm holdings in Maio are about 4.3 times those of Santo Antao (Table 2.12). The very large standard deviations (and wide ranges) especially in the case of Maio (Table 2.12) is an indication of the existence of a few relatively large farms and many small farm plots.

Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in m²) – Men (HHH) respondents

		Household (HH) farms (A)	Individual men farms (B)	Individual women's farms (C)	Household farm holding (A+B+C)
Santo Antao	Average area	1,483	3,000	0	4,483
	Std. Dev.	2,275	-	-	2,275
	Max	10,000	3,000	0	13,000
	Min	15	3,000	0	3,015
Maio	Average area	19,413	0	0	19,413
	Std. Dev.	25,724	-	-	25,724
	Max	100,000	0	0	100,000
	Min	200	0	0	200

Note: 1 acre =4046.86 m²

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH) and individual men farm sizes (Santo Antao and Maio)

Table 2.13: Household and individual farm sizes (in m²) – Women (WiHH) respondents

	Santo Antao			
	Household (HH) farms (A)	Individual men farms (B)	Individual women farms (C)	Household farm holding (A+B+C)
Average area (m ²)	573	0	700	1,273
Std. Dev.	-	-	415	415
Max	1,000	0	700	1,700
Min	20	0	700	720

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Figure 2.3: Distribution of household (HH) and individual women farm sizes (according to WiHHs – Santo Antao)

2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming

There are differences in the methods of land acquisition for farming by men in the two islands. In Santo Antao, the main sources of land for farming are inheritance and the state, while in Maio it is inheritance and usufruct rights (Table 2.14 and Figure 2.4). In the case of women, it is sharecropping and purchase (in Santo Antao) (Table 2.15). The results however tend to indicate that these land acquisitions apply only to household farm plots. There was not much response with respect to individual farm plots. Also, the results suggest that women have more serious land acquisition constraints compared to men in Santo Antao. Even though the level of response was very low (Table 2.15), there is no indication from the few who responded that they inherit any land nor obtain any from the state. Women not being able to inherit land is a general problem in Africa but why the women do not have access to the land owned by the state which men have access to is not clear. There is a need for clarification on that. In-depth study of land use in the country will be useful so that the very limited land can be used more effectively and judiciously.

Table 2.14: Methods of land acquisition for farming according to men (HHH)

Method of land acquisition	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Total	
	Santo Antao	Maio	Santo Antao	Maio	Santo Antao	Maio
	% Freq	% Freq	% Freq	% Freq	% Freq	% Freq
Inheritance	15 (39.5)	5 (31.3)	0 (0.0)	-	15 (38.5)	5 (31.3)
Leased	3 (7.9)	-	0 (0.0)	-	3 (7.7)	-
Owned/Bought	2 (5.3)	2 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	-	2 (5.1)	2 (12.5)
Borrowed (Free)	2 (5.3)	2 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	-	2 (5.1)	2 (12.5)
State owned	11 (28.9)	1 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	-	11 (28.2)	1 (6.3)
Share cropping	5 (13.2)	-	1 (100.0)	-	6 (15.4)	-
Usufruct	0 (0.0)	5 (31.3)	-	-	-	5 (31.3)
Loaned	-	1 (6.3)	-	-	-	1 (6.3)
Husband's land	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-	0 (0.0)	-
Total	38 (100.0)	16 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	-	39 (100.0)	16 (100.0)

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Figure 2.4: Methods of land acquisition (according to HHHs)

Table 2.15: Methods of land acquisition for farming according to women (WiHH) – Santo Antao

Method of land acquisition	HH farm plots	Individual women farm plots	Total
	Santo Antao	Santo Antao	Santo Antao
	% Freq	% Freq	% Freq
Inheritance	-	-	-
Leased	-	-	-
Owned/Bought	-	-	-
Borrowed (Free)	-	-	-
State owned	-	-	-
Share cropping	3 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (50.0)
Owned/ Bought	2 (40.0)	1 (100.0)	3 (50.0)
Total	5 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	6 (100.0)

Source. Field survey, May 2023

2.3.3 Land preparation methods

Table 2.16 shows that farmers use only the hoe to prepare their land for crop cultivation. The use of weedicides is banned in Cape Verde and the lands are too small for use of tractor. There is need for the development of small mechanical tools and equipment that can help the farmer to cultivate the land more efficiently.

Table 2.16: Land preparation methods

Island	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots	Individual men farm plots	Individual women farm plots	Total
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Santo Antao	Tractor	-	-	-	-
	Hoe	39	1	-	40
	Others	-	-	-	-
	Total	39	1	-	40
Maio	Tractor	-	-	-	-
	Hoe	16	-	-	16
	Others	-	-	-	-
	Total	16	-	-	16
Total (both Islands)	Tractor	-	-	-	-
	Hoe	55	1	-	56
	Others	-	-	-	-
	Total	55	1	-	56

Source. Field survey, May 2023

2.3.4 Numbers of farm plots and their locations

In both Santo Antao and Maio, there are compound and bush farms. The number of bush farm plots tend to be much higher than the compound farm plots especially in Maio (Tables 2.17, 2.18 and 2.19). The bush farms in Maio are also very far from homesteads, over 30 minutes walking time is required to get to the bush farms on average (Table 2.18). The women in Santo Antao also indicated the greater dominance of bush farms (Table 2.19).

Table 2.17: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms - Santo Antao (HHH)

Farm Plot category	Compound farm		Bush farm		Total numbers of farm plots per household	Average time spent (minutes) to travel from home to farms (the bush farms)
	No of farm plots per HH	% number of farm plots	No of farm plots per HH	% number of farm plots		
HH farm plots	2	33.3	4	66.7	6	23
Individual men farm plots	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	NA
Individual women farm plots	1	100.0	0	0.0	1	NA
Total	3	42.9	4	57.1	7	-

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.18: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms - Maio (HHH)

Farm Plot category	Compound farm		Bush farm		Total numbers of farm plots per household	Average time spent (minutes) to travel from home to farms (the bush farms)
	No of farm plots per HH	% number of farm plots	No of farm plots per HH	% number of farm plots		
HH farm plots	2	12.5	14	87.5	16	38
Individual men farm plots	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	NA
Individual women farm plots	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	NA
Total	2	12.5	14	87.5	16	

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.19: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms – Santo Antao (WiHH)

Farm category	Plot	Compound farm		Bush farm		Average time spent to travel from home to farms (the bush farms)		
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Number of farm plots	Mean distance (minutes)	Standard deviation
HH farm plots		2	33.3	4	66.7	5	23	23.08
Individual men farm plots		-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Individual women farm plots		1	100.0	0	0.0	1	1	.-

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming

2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots

Men farmers' perceived level of soil fertility of their household and individual farms are presented in Table 2.20. On average, most of the men farmers in both Santo Antao and Maio (49% and 81% respectively) perceived their household farms to be fertile but still require some external inputs and manure. Only about 8% and 12.5% of men farmers, in Santo Antao and Maio respectively perceived their soils to be very fertile (Table 2.20). While over 20% of the farmers in Santo Antao indicated that their soils are poor, none of the farmers in Maio perceived their soils to be poor. In the case of the women farmers in Santo Antao, most of them (about 85%) perceive their soils to be just average requiring external inputs and/or manure every year (Table 2.21).

Table 2.20: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots by men (HHH)

Island	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	3	7.7	1	100.0	4	10.0
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	19	48.7	0	0.0	19	47.5
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	8	20.5	0	0.0	8	20.0
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	8	20.5	0	0.0	8	20.0
	Other	1	2.6	0	0.0	1	2.5
	Total	39	100.0	1	100.0	40	100.0
Maio	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	2	12.5	0	0.0	2	12.5
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	13	81.3	0	0.0	13	81.3
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	1	6.3	0	0.0	1	6.3
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Other	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
		Total	16	100.0	0	0.0	16

Source. Field survey, May 2023

Table 2.21: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots by women (WiHH)

Island	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	4	16.0	0	0.0	4	15.4
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	21	84.0	1	100.0	22	84.6
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total	25	100.0	1	100.0	26	100.0

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

2.4.2 Use of inorganic and organic fertilizers by men and women farmers

Tables 2.22 and 2.23 indicate that most men and women farmers in the two islands do not use inorganic fertilizers on their farms. Tables 2.24 and 2.25, however, indicate that all use organic manure on their farms. That is very good information for the promotion of agroecological practices. It is indication that Cape Verde is a very good place to showcase innovative agroecological practices.

Table 2.22: Inorganic fertilizer utilization by men farmers (HHH)

Island		Farms						Total	
		Household (HH) farms plots		Individual Men farms plots		Individual Women farm plots			
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Yes	15	38.5	0	0.0	-	-	15	37.5
	No	24	61.5	1	100.0	-	-	25	62.5
	Total	39	100.0	1	100.0	-	-	40	100.0
Maio	Yes	1	6.3	-	-	-	-	1	6.3
	No	15	93.8	-	-	-	-	15	93.8
	Total	16	100.0	-	-	-	-	16	100.0

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.23: Inorganic fertilizer utilization by women in Santo Antao (WiHH)

Island		Farms						Total	
		Household (HH) farms plots		Individual Men farms plots		Individual Women farm plots			
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Yes	1	20.0	-	-	0	0.0	1	16.7
	No	4	80.0	-	-	1	100.0	5	83.3
	Total	5	100.0	-	-	1	100.0	6	100.0

Source. Field survey, May 2023

Table 2.24: Organic fertilizer utilization by men in Santo Antao and Maio (HHH)

Island		Farms						Total	
		Household (HH) farms plots		Individual Men farms plots		Individual Women farm plots			
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Yes	36	92.3	1	100.0	-	-	37	92.5
	No	3	7.7	0	0.0	-	-	3	7.5
	Total	39	100.0	1	100.0	-	-	40	100.0
Maio	Yes	16	100.0	-	-	-	-	16	100.0
	No	0	0.0	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
	Total	16	100.0	-	-	-	-	16	100.0

Source. Field survey, May 2023

Table 2.25: Organic fertilizer utilization by women in Santo Antao (WiHH)

District		Farms						Total	
		Household (HH) farms plots		Individual Men farms plots		Individual Women farm plots			
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Yes	5	83.3	-	-	1	100.0	6	85.7
	No	1	16.7	-	-	0	0.0	1	14.3
	Total	6	100.0	-	-	1	100.0	7	100.0

Source. Field survey, May 2023

CHAPTER 3

FARMING SYSTEMS IN THE ISLANDS

3.1 Crop-Based Systems

3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures

Mixed cropping is the prevalent practice in both islands. The cropping systems of the areas are captured by noting the crops and crop mixtures that are planted in the household as well as the individual men and women farm plots. Crop mixtures range from two to seven or even more. Most of the production is rainfed, thus one of the main reasons for crop mixtures is to reduce the risk of crop failure due to the many risk factors.

Table 3.1: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in Santo Antao

Crop Mixtures	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Maize/Pigeon pea/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)	3	7.5	1	100	0	0.0
Sugarcane	3	7.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Maize/Pigeon pea	3	7.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Carrots	3	7.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Carrots	3	7.5	1	100	0	0.0
Beans (Cowpea)/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)	3	7.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Beans (Cowpea)/Potato (English/Irish)	3	7.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato	2	5.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Maize/Pigeon pea/Feijoca/Feijão Fava (Phaseolus coccineus)/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)	2	5.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Carrots/Tomatoes	2	5.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Yam/Sweet potato/Carrots/Tomatoes/Other	2	5.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Tomatoes	1	2.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)/Carrots/Tomatoes/Pumpkin	1	2.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)/Carrots/ Pepper/Tomatoes/Onions	1	2.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Potato/ (English/Irish) /Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/ Tomatoes/ Onions	1	2.5	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The 15 most common crop/crop mixtures as captured by the survey for each of the islands are given in Tables 3.1 and 3.2 for Santo Antao and Maio respectively. There were only two responses for individual men crops and none for individual women crops in the case of the HHH (men) questionnaire for Santo Antao, and for Maio, there were only HH farm plots.

Table 3.2: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in Maio

Crop/Crop Mixtures	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women's farm plots	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Sweet potato/Onions	3	18.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cassava/Sweet potato/Onions	3	18.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)/Tomatoes/Onions	2	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Tomatoes	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/ Onions/Sugarcane	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/ Onions/Pumpkin	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/ Carrots/Tomatoes/Onions	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/ Carrots/Onions/Pawpaw /Papaya/Banana	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Maize/Pigeon pea/ Feijoca/Feijão Fava (phaseolus coccineus)/Sweet potato/Onions	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cassava/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)/Tomatoes	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Tomatoes	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/Onions/Sugarcane	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato /Onions/Pumpkin	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato/ Carrots/Tomatoes/ Onions	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The tables show how very complex the cropping systems are, even in the small areas they cultivate. Crops that dominate in the mixtures in Santo Antao are sweet potato, Irish potato, maize and carrots while sweet potato and onions are in almost all plots in Maio. Table 3.3 gives the common mixtures in the women plots in Santo Antao.

Table 3.3: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in women headed households (HHH) in Santo Antao

Crop Mixtures
Sweet potato/Carrots/Tomatoes
Sweet potato/Carrots
Maize/Pigeon pea/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)
Maize/Pigeon pea
Maize/Beans (Cowpea)/Sweet potato/Potato (English/Irish)
Maize/ Bambara/groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)
Carrots/Tomatoes

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Relative importance of crops to the people can be partly inferred by the number of times the crops appear in the various crop/crop mixtures. Tables 3.4 and 3.5 give that information for Santo Antao and Maio respectively. Sweet potato, maize, pigeon pea, Irish potato and vegetables (carrots, tomatoes and onions) are the main food crops in Santo Antao. Sugarcane is a main cash crop (Table 3.4). In the case of Maio, sweet potatoes, onions and Irish potatoes are the important crops (Table 3.5).

Table 3.4: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Santo Antao

Crop	HH farm plots	
	Freq.	% Freq
Sweet potato	18	17.3
Maize	13	12.5
Pigeon pea	13	12.5
Potato (English/Irish)	13	12.5
Carrots	11	10.6
Tomatoes	8	7.7
Onions	6	5.8
Sugarcane	4	3.8
Pumpkin	4	3.8
Beans (Cowpea)	2	1.9
Feijoca/Feijão Fava (<i>Phaseolus coccineous</i>)	2	1.9
Leafy vegetables (local)	2	1.9
Pepper	2	1.9
Yam	1	1.0
Cassava	1	1.0
Rice	1	1.0
Coffee	1	1.0
Melon	1	1.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.5: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Maio

Crop	HH farm plots	
	Freq	% Freq
Sweet potato	16	32.0
Onions	13	26.0
Potato (English/Irish)	3	6.0
Carrots	2	4.0
Fejioca/Fejao Fava(Phaseolus, coccineus)	1	2.0
Maize	1	2.0
Sugarcane	1	2.0
Pumpkin	1	2.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

3.1.2 Planting materials and sources

The types of planting materials and source of acquisition vary from person to person in both Islands. Tables 3.6, 3.7, and 3.8 present results of the types and sources of planting materials in the Santo Antao and Maio respectively. The results from both household heads (HHs) and women in household (WiHHs) indicate that a significant number of farmers from the Santo Antao Island use indigenous seed from their own storages. Though the data on Maio is quite sparse, the results show that farmers use local vines of sweet potato (the commonest crop among farmers) and they acquire most vines from other farmers.

Table 3.6: Types and sources of planting materials- Santo Antao HHH

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	12	1	-	-
	Improved (Open-pollinated)	1	1	-	-
Pumpkin	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Pepper	“Improved hybrid”	-	-	-	1
Other	Indigenous	1	-	-	0
	“Improved”	0	-	-	2
Sweet potato	Indigenous	8	1	8	-
Feijoca/ Feijão fava	Indigenous	2	-	-	-
Vegetables	Improved, (hybrid)	-	-	-	3
Carrots	Indigenous	1	1	-	0
	“Improved”	0	0	-	1
	Improved, (Hybrid)	0	0	-	6
Soybeans	Indigenous	5	1	1	1
Cassava	Indigenous	-	-	2	-
Sugarcane	Indigenous	1	1	-	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.7: Types and sources of planting materials- Maio HHH

Type of seeds used		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Pumpkin	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Sugarcane	Indigenous	-	-	1	-
Potato	“Improved”	-	-	-	2
Sweet potato	Indigenous (local)	1	-	13	1
Cassava	Indigenous	-	-	1	-
Onion	Indigenous	-	-	-	1
	“Improved”	-	-	-	1

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- Santo Antao WiHH

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	3	1	-	-
	Improved (Open-pollinated)	1	1	-	-
Onion	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Potato	Indigenous	3	-	-	-
	“Improved hybrid”	-	-	-	1
Other	Indigenous	1	-	-	0
	“Improved”	0	-	-	2
Sweet potato	Indigenous	3	4	2	-
Feijoca/ Feijão fava	Indigenous	-	2	-	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

3.1.3 Soil amendment practices

The main soil amendment practice in Santo Antao and Maio Islands is the use of manure (organic materials). As indicated in Table 3.9, about 52% and 92% of respondents in the Santo Antao and Maio Islands respectively indicated that their households use organic materials to fertilize farmlands. Similarly, about 75% of the women in household respondents in Santo Antao said they use organic materials to fertilize farmlands. Other means of fertilizing farmlands included crop rotation and fallow lands. These results are an indication of the possibility of success of agroecological practices in the area.

Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH

Soil amendment practices	Santo Antao		Maio	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Use of manure (organic materials)	11	52.4	12	92.3
Land fallow	1	4.8	1	7.7
Crop rotation	5	23.8	0	0.0
Other	4	19.0	0	0.0
Total	21	100.0	13	100.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH

Soil amendment practices	Santo Antao	
	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	1	12.5
Use of manure (organic materials)	6	75.0
Land fallow	1	12.5
Total	8	100.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

3.1.4 Crop production constraints

Crop production can face various constraints that impact agricultural productivity. These constraints may differ by gender, island or agroecological zone. In the Santo Antao Island, the first three most significant crop production constraints identified by men (HHH) are pests and diseases, erratic rainfall, and access to labor scarcity. In the case of the Maio Island, the main constraints identified were erratic rainfall, pests and diseases, and access to production inputs (Figure 3.1)¹.

¹ Details of how the weighted scores are computed in the write-up are in the Appendix 2.

Figure 3.1: Household heads (men) crop production constraints by Island

Despite common crop production constraints shared between Santo Antao and Maio Islands among household heads, certain limitations such as small farm sizes, erosion, soil fertility, and access to farming land are unique to household heads in Santo Antao island. The constraints discussed during focus group discussions in both Santo Antao and Maio Islands include lack of water, inadequate crop quantity, pest and disease outbreaks, insufficient manure for soil replenishment, low soil fertility, high temperatures and heat waves, lack of quality seeds, limited road access leading to restricted sales markets, and scarcity of qualified labor.

During key informant interviews (KIIs) in Santo Antao, the majority of crop production constraints were confirmed. Challenges highlighted included pests, water scarcity, manpower (labour) shortages, extreme hot and dry weather conditions, and constant wind. The most prominent constraints identified are pests and diseases. The problem of millipedes hindering the cultivation of common potatoes was particularly stressed during key informant interviews.

For women, the three main crop production constraints in Santo Antao island are erratic rainfall, pests and diseases, and finance (Figure 3.2). Other constraints include issues related to soil fertility, weed management, soil erosion, and land ownership.

Figure 3.2 WiHH crop production constraints – Santo Antao

The crop production challenges reported by women in the survey were confirmed during the focus group discussions (FGDs). Women mentioned that outbreaks of lice and aphids in vegetable crops are common, as are fungal infections such as powdery mildew and rust. The presence of "mil-pés," a small centipede that feeds on tubers and roots is also a significant cause of production losses. It has led to embargoes on the marketing of products from Casa do Meio (Santo Antao Island) to other islands.

In Santo Antao, access to labor is a significant constraint for men, whereas access to production inputs is highlighted as a major concern for men in Maio. Women in Santo Antao face a broader range of constraints compared to men, including finance-related challenges. The contrast between men's and women's constraints in Santo Antao highlights gender disparities in agricultural challenges. Women often face a broader range of constraints, including financial limitations, which may be attributed to unequal access to resources, land, and decision-making power. During the key informant interviews in Maio, it was also mentioned that the lack of rain and the local population's inability to adapt to new forms of cultivation are significant challenges. "There is lack of water for irrigation, so we only practice rainfed agriculture here, unlike in the past when it wasn't so difficult to obtain water for irrigation", was a common statement in Maio by key informants.

Given the complex and interconnected nature of crop production constraints, interventions should adopt integrated approaches that address multiple challenges simultaneously. This could involve strategies such as promoting sustainable land management practices, improving access to agricultural inputs and technologies, strengthening pest and disease management systems, and enhancing financial inclusion for smallholder farmers, with a particular focus on empowering women farmers.

3.2 Livestock-Based Systems

3.2.1 Animal ownership and management

Livestock-based systems play a crucial role in sustaining rural livelihoods and ensuring food security in Santo Antao and Maio islands. Understanding the dynamics of animal ownership and management by gender in specific districts is essential for informed agricultural development. Tables 3.11, 3.12, and 3.13 provide distinct practices of animal ownership and management in the Santo Antao and Maio islands, with a focus on men (household heads) and women.

In the Santo Antao Island, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including cattle, sheep and goats as well as donkeys, pigs, and fowls (chickens) (Table 3.11).

Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Santo Antao Island for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	1.4	0.55	0.2	0.45	1.0	0.71	0.2	0.447
Donkeys	1.0	0.0	-	-	1.0	-	-	-
Sheep	10.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	10.0	0.0	1	0.0
Goats	17.5	17.98	3.9	14.55	15.4	15.05	0.2	0.943
Pigs	1.8	0.98	1.2	1.14	1.5	0.69	0.3	0.647
Fowls (Chickens)	17.0	14.02	1.4	3.78	21.0	16.94	-	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 1.4, with a standard deviation (SD) of about 0.55. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 1, with an SD of 0.71. Donkey ownership averaged 1 in 2022, while sheep ownership averaged 10, and goats averaged 18. In 2023, donkey and sheep average ownership remained constant, while the average number of goats owned declined by 2. Pigs and fowls (chickens) ownership averaged 1.82 and 17, respectively, in 2022. In 2023, pig ownership declined to 1.45 while fowl ownership increased to 21. From Table 3.11, there is consistency in the average numbers of livestock owned and sold in 2022 and 2023, respectively. The decrease in the average ownership of cattle and goats coincided with an increase in fowl ownership, suggesting a growing shift or dominance of poultry in Santo Antao Island. The increased ownership of fowls points to stability or growth in poultry farming, possibly due to their faster income generation. As confirmed during the focus group discussions, pigs, chickens, and cattle are essentially confined and fed, hence the small average numbers owned. In contrast, goats move freely through the landscape, feeding on spontaneous vegetation, and may stay overnight in corrals inside or outside the locality,

resulting in higher numbers compared to all other livestock. This is also due to the added economic value of milk.

Women owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including non-ruminants such as donkeys and pigs, small ruminants like goats, and fowls (chickens) (Table 3.12).

Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Santo Antao Island for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Donkeys	4.6	2.70	-	-	4.8	2.78	-	-
Goats	21.5	20.64	3.4	5.04	16.4	20.91	2.8	4.37
Pigs	1.5	0.58	0.8	0.96	1.8	0.96	0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	12.3	9.40	-	-	15.8	12.02	-	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

In 2022, the average donkey ownership by women was 4.6, with no sales. By 2023, the average donkey ownership slightly increased to 4.8, with no sales. Among women in Santo Antao Island, goat ownership averaged 21.5 in 2022, with a standard deviation (SD) of 20.64, while pigs averaged 1.5 with an SD of 0.56. In 2023, goat ownership declined to 16.38, while pig ownership rose to 1.75. Fowl (chicken) ownership averaged 12 in 2022. In 2023, fowl ownership increased to 15.83. There were no sales of fowls (chickens) in 2022 and 2023, respectively.

There are distinct differences in livestock ownership patterns and trends between men and women in the years 2022 and 2023 in Santo Antao Island. Men typically exhibit lower average ownership of donkeys compared to women. On the other hand, women tend to have higher average ownership of goats and pigs compared to men. Conversely, women tend to have lower average ownership of fowls (chickens) compared to men.

In the Maio Island, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, non-ruminants like pigs, fowls (chickens) and ducks (Table 3.13).

Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Maio island for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	4.86	3.671	0.57	0.787	4.57	2.82	0.14	0.378
Sheep	12	-	0	-	10	-	0	-
Goats	34.55	44.996	5.91	11.58	26.91	26.319	4.55	10.27
Pigs	4.71	1.976	1.57	1.618	4	4.082	0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	43.33	54.368	8.83	11.321	33.83	28.174	4.67	8.165
Duck	24	-	2	-	40	-	0	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 4.86, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 3.67. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 4.57, with an SD of 2.82. Sheep ownership averaged 12 in 2022, while goats averaged 34.55. In 2023, sheep ownership declined to 10, and goat ownership also decreased to 26.91. Pigs, fowl, and duck ownership averaged 4.71, 43, and 24, respectively, in 2022. However, in 2023, pig ownership declined to 4, fowl to 33.83, while duck ownership increased to 40. Cattle, goats, pigs, and fowl (chickens) benefited from sales in 2022 and 2023, while sheep and ducks experienced no sales within the period.

The decline in average cattle ownership in Maio island by men from 2022 to 2023 suggests a potential shift in agricultural practices that may affect cattle farming albeit not intense. Similarly, decreases in sheep and goat ownership indicate changes in livestock preferences or market demands. The fluctuations in pig, fowl, and duck ownership alongside changes in sales, suggest shifts in production or consumption patterns.

3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics

Animal breeds

Animal breeds may vary based on geographical locations and gender-specific practices. Tables 3.14 and 3.15 show the different types of breeds reared by household heads and women in households on Santo Antao and Maio islands. The livestock breeds commonly reared by men on Santo Antao and Maio islands are mostly indigenous or local breeds, with some cases of crossbred or exotic types (Table 3.14).

Tables 3.14: Livestock breeds reared by men in Santo Antao and Maio islands

Type breeds reared		Santo Antao	Maio
		Freq.	Freq.
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	3	7
	Crossbred	0	1
	Exotic	0	0
Goats	Indigenous	17	4
	Crossbred	0	3
	Exotic	0	1
Pigs	Indigenous	6	5
	Crossbred	1	1
	Exotic	1	0
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	5	3
	Crossbred	0	0
	Exotic	0	1
Donkeys	Indigenous	1	0
	Crossbred	0	0
	Exotic	0	0
Sheep	Indigenous	0	1
	Crossbred	0	0
	Exotic	0	0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The indigenous livestock breeds commonly reared by men in Santo Antao and Maio islands differed sparingly. They include goats, fowls (chickens), and cattle (Table 3.14). Pigs are not only indigenous but also reared as crossbred/exotic in both Santo Antao and Maio islands. For women in households, all the livestock types including goats, pigs, fowls, and donkeys reared in Santo Antao are indigenous (Table 3.15).

Table 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by women in Santo Antao

Type breeds reared		Freq.
Goats	Indigenous	7
	Crossbred	0
	Exotic	0
Pigs	Indigenous	4
	Crossbred	0
	Exotic	0
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	3
	Crossbred	1
	Exotic	0
Donkeys	Indigenous	5
	Crossbred	0
	Exotic	0

While both men and women engage in livestock rearing in Santo Antao and Maio islands, they differ in the variety of livestock reared and breeding practices employed. Men primarily rear goats, fowls (chickens), cattle, and crossbred/exotic pigs. In contrast, women rear a wider variety of livestock including goats, pigs, fowls, and donkeys. While men rear both indigenous and crossbred/exotic pigs, women exclusively rear indigenous pigs.

Sources of Animal breeds

The main source from which the animals are obtained varies based on the type of animal (Tables 3.16 and 3.17). In the Santo Antao Island, Table 3.16 shows that the men livestock breed sources are local (given by other farmers), local (purchased) and own breed. Cattle breed produced by men are purchased locally. For donkeys, fowls (chickens), goats, and pigs reared by men, the main source of these animal breeds is owned. Pigs are the only livestock reared by men where the breeding stock is purchased from exotic sources.

According to Table 3.16, most indigenous breeds reared by women are either locally sourced through purchases or owned. Specifically, 86% of women's goat breeds are owned by farmers, while 14% are purchased locally. For fowls and donkeys, more than half of the indigenous breeds are owned by farmers, while the remaining portion is purchased locally. Conversely, for pigs, 75% of the breeds are locally purchased by women. While both men and women on Santo Antao Island acquire livestock breeds from local sources and predominantly own certain breeds, they differ in their main sources of obtaining livestock and in the involvement of exotic sources, particularly in pig breeds.

Table 3.16 Men and women sources of animal breeds in Santo Antao

Animal	Exotic- (purchased)	Local – (given by other farmers)	Local – purchased	Own breed
	Freq	Freq.	Freq.	Freq.
Men in household (HHH)				
Cattle	0	1	2	0
Donkeys	0	0	0	1
Fowls (chickens)	0	1	1	3
Goats	0	4	2	11
Pigs	1	1	2	4
Women in household (WiHH)				
Donkeys	0	0	1	4
Fowls (chickens)	0	0	2	3
Goats	0	0	1	6
Pigs	0	0	3	1

Source: Field survey, May 2023

On Maio Island, Table 3.17 indicates that all indigenous breeds of sheep are purchased locally. The sources of livestock breed for men, such as cattle, fowls, goats, and pigs, range from exotic sources (purchased or given by other farmers locally) to those purchased or owned locally. Most cattle and pig breeds are locally purchased. Most fowl breeds are owned, with a quarter being purchased from exotic sources or locally. The majority of goat breeds are purchased from exotic sources by men in Maio, while a quarter are purchased locally or owned by the farmer.

Table 3.17 Men main source of animal breeds in Maio

Animal	Exotic- (purchased)		Local – (given by other farmers)		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Cattle	1	12.5	0	0.0	6	75.0	1	12.5
Fowls (chickens)	1	25.0	0	0.0	1	25.0	2	50.0
Goats	3	37.5	1	12.5	2	25.0	2	25.0
Pigs	1	16.7	0	0.0	4	66.7	1	16.7
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Special characteristics of animal breeds

Animal breeds exhibit unique traits or features that set one breed apart from another. Tables 3.18 and 3.19 showcase the distinct characteristics of animals for men and women in Santo Antao and Maio Islands.

On Santo Antao Island, the majority of men in households indicated that cattle breeds are known for producing a lot of manure. Others attributed special characteristics to cattle in terms of high productivity (meat and milk), good taste (20%), and easy availability within the island (Table 3.18). All household heads interviewed referred to donkeys as hardy and resilient to their environment, whereas for women, donkeys are also characterized as hardy, disease-resistant, and easily available. Fowls (chickens) are characterized by men as easily available (33.3%), highly productive (meat and eggs) (25%), disease-resistant (17%), good taste (17%), and hardy (8.3%), whereas for women, they characterize fowl as having good taste (29%), easy availability (21%), and disease resistance (21%).

Table 3.18: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in Santo Antao Island

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg)		Hardy (resilient in environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads (men)												
Cattle	1	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	20.0	1	20.0	2	40.0
Donkeys	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Goats	3	7.9	13	34.2	4	10.5	3	7.9	10	26.3	5	13.2
Fowls (Chickens)	3	25.0	1	8.3	2	16.7	2	16.7	4	33.3	0	0.0
Pigs	5	26.3	1	5.3	4	21.1	4	21.1	5	26.3	0	0.0
Women in household												
Donkeys	0	0.0	4	57.1	2	28.6	0	0.0	1	14.3	0	0.0
Goats	4	23.5	5	29.4	1	5.9	4	23.5	3	17.6	0	0.0
Fowls (Chickens)	2	14.3	2	14.3	3	21.4	4	28.6	3	21.4	0	0.0
Pigs	1	7.7	3	23.1	3	23.1	3	23.1	2	15.4	1	7.7

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Pigs, like fowls, are easily available (26%), highly productive (meat) (21%), disease-resistant (21%), good-tasting (21%), and hardy (5%). Conversely, for women in Santo Antao, pigs are characterized by their hardiness (23%), disease resistance (23%), and good taste (23%). Other women perceive pigs to be easily available (15%) and productive (meat) (Table 3.18).

On Maio Island, the majority of men in households indicated that cattle breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat and milk (35%), easily available (18%), and producing a lot of manure (29%). Additionally, cattle breeds were described by 5.9% each as being hardy, disease-resistant, and having good taste (Table 3.19).

Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads in Maio island

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg etc)		Hardy (resilient in environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cattle	6	35.3	1	5.9	1	5.9	1	5.9	3	17.6	5	29.4
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Goats	6	35.3	2	11.8	2	11.8	2	11.8	2	11.8	3	17.6
Pigs	4	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	50.0	2	16.7	0	0.0
Fowls (Chickens)	3	42.9	2	28.6	1	14.3	0	0.0	1	14.3	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

Most household heads (men) attribute special characteristics to goats, fowls, and pigs, noting their high productivity, good taste, and easy availability. Goats are especially noted for their hardiness, disease resistance, and ability to produce ample manure. Fowls are recognized for their high productivity, particularly in egg production, as well as their hardiness, disease resistance, and easy availability in Maio (Table 3.19).

3.2.3 Livestock constraints

Livestock production encounters diverse constraints that may affect its efficiency, with variations observed across districts, genders, and types of livestock, including large ruminants (e.g. cattle), small ruminants (e.g. goats and sheep), non-ruminants (e.g. donkeys, pigs) and poultry (e.g. fowls - chickens and guinea fowls). Figures 3.3 to 3.4 illustrate the distinct types of livestock and the constraints experienced by household heads (men) and women in the Santo Antao and Maio islands.

Cattle production constraints

Figures 3.3 illustrate the cattle production constraints faced by household heads (men) on the Santo Antao and Maio islands. Lack of feed during the dry season, diseases, and lack of water in the dry season are the primary cattle production constraints among household heads in both islands (Figure 3.3). Although these constraints, especially the lack of feed during the dry season and diseases, are indicated to be more acute in Santo Antao, difficulties in accessing veterinary services and information on livestock management are isolated constraints on Santo Antao, whereas issues of financing and poor housing are isolated cases in Maio among household heads. Lack of water during the dry season is more prevalent among household heads in Maio compared to Santo Antao (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Household head cattle production constraints by island

Goat production constraints

Figures 3.4 and 3.5 illustrate the goat production constraints faced by household heads (men) and women on Santo Antao and Maio islands. In Santo Antao, men's goat production constraints include diseases, lack of water and feed during the dry season, poor housing, difficulties accessing veterinary services, theft, among others. On Maio island, men's constraints comprise lack of water and feed during the dry season, poor housing, theft, and financing (Figure 3.4). Although the constraints for households (men) may be similar in both islands, the priorities differ. Disease infestation and access to veterinary services are peculiar situations in Santo Antao. The unique situation of disease infestation and limited access to veterinary services suggests that livestock, especially goat production in Santo Antao, may be more vulnerable to health issues. As discussed by participants in the focus group sessions, the lack of animal healthcare emerged as a significant concern at the local level. There is a general perception that external veterinary assistance is lacking, and there is a need for individual capacity building among producers in animal health and nutrition. This vulnerability could have adverse effects on livestock productivity, reproduction rates, and overall well-being, thereby impacting the livelihoods of farmers and communities dependent on goat production. While both islands reported theft as a major constraint in goat production, it is more pronounced in Maio island, along with challenges in accessing feed during the dry season and financing.

For women in household, which is only in Santo Antao, the constraints are related to diseases, lack of feed in dry season, access to vet services, lack of water in dry season, poor housing, lack of market and access to information on livestock management (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.4: Household head (men) goat production constraints by island

Figure 3.5: Women goat production constraints in Santo Antao

While both Santo Antao and Maio share common challenges in goat production, Santo Antao stands out for the breadth and complexity of constraints faced by women in particular. Particularly among women, Santo Antao exhibits a diverse array of constraints that extend beyond those faced by men and those observed in Maio. The inclusion of market access and information dissemination as constraints for women highlights broader systemic issues impacting goat production and livelihoods in Santo Antao. During the focus group discussions, participants noted the absence of a market for locally produced meat. Typically, meat has to be sold in the form of live animals, resulting in reduced income for producers compared to a cut-and-sell scenario. The existence of a nearby slaughterhouse or butcher was proposed as a potential solution to this problem not only for goats but also pigs and chicken. Maio, while facing similar challenges as Santo Antao in terms of basic infrastructure and resource access,

appears to have a relatively narrower range of constraints, with theft emerging as a significant concern by household heads.

Sheep production constraints

Figures 3.6 show the sheep production constraints for household heads (men) in Santo Antao and Maio islands. In Santo Antao, men's most pressing sheep production constraints are diseases and a lack of feed during the dry season. In Maio islands, the constraints for men are related to a lack of feed during the dry season and poor housing (Figure 3.6). The implication is that, in Santo Antao, efforts may need to be directed towards disease control measures and improving access to feed during the dry season, while in Maio, interventions may prioritize improving feed availability and housing conditions. However, there was no report on the constraints in sheep production for women. The absence of documented constraints for women in sheep production underscores the possibility that the contributions and roles of women in sheep production might be disregarded or underestimated.

Figure 3.6: Household head sheep production constraints by island

For both large and small ruminants, certain constraints are consistent. As highlighted during the focus group discussions, the lack of feed and water during the dry season poses significant challenges. Participants noted that the scarcity of pasture throughout the year, attributed to the region's pronounced water scarcity, stands out as a primary concern for farmers. This shortage necessitates the purchase of fodder or supplemental feed to support free grazing practices. To mitigate these challenges, discussions emphasized the importance of collecting, treating, and conserving fodder during peak growing seasons to ensure a year-round food supply. Such practices not only address feed shortages but also help mitigate the environmental impacts associated with uncontrolled grazing.

Moreover, the scarcity of drinking water emerged as another significant constraint affecting livestock activities. Participants proposed several measures to improve water provision for animals, including investments in groundwater abstraction and reservoirs, the construction of

dikes and dams to capture runoff water, and the acquisition of auto tanks for water transportation within the community.

Pig production constraints

Figures 3.7 and 3.8 show the pig production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Santo Antao and Maio islands, respectively.

Figure 3.7 Household head pig production constraints by island

In Santo Antao, men face various constraints in pig production, including diseases, lack of feed during the dry season, limited access to veterinary services, poor housing, insufficient water during the dry season, lack of market access, and time constraints. In Maio islands, men encounter challenges such as lack of feed during the dry season, diseases, theft, and financing issues (Figure 3.7).

For women in households depicted in Figure 3.8, which primarily applies to Santo Antao, their pig production constraints include diseases, limited access to veterinary services, poor housing, water scarcity during the dry season, limited access to information on livestock management, and financing challenges.

Figure 3.8 Women in household pig production constraints in Santo Antao Island

Fowls (chicken) production constraints

Figures 3.9 and 3.10 show the fowl (chicken) production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Santo Antao and Maio islands, respectively. In Santo Antao, men's most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints are the incidence of diseases and lack of time to manage chickens. On Maio island, the constraints for men are the lack of feed in the dry season and financing (Figure 3.9). This suggests that household heads involved in fowl production in Santo Antao and Maio islands face distinct challenges, particularly concerning disease management, time allocation, feed availability, and financial resources.

Figure 3.9 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by island

For women (Figure 3.10), largely specific to Santo Antao Island, the most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints include diseases, poor housing, limited access to veterinary services, limited access to information on livestock management, lack of market access, and lack of feed during the dry season. The diverse array of constraints suggests that improving fowl production outcomes for women in Santo Antao requires addressing multiple interconnected issues. This may include improving access to veterinary care, implementing training programs on disease prevention and management, enhancing housing infrastructure, disseminating information on livestock management practices more effectively, and facilitating market access and feed availability.

Figure 3.10 Women fowl (chicken) production constraints Santo Antao Island

3.3 Irrigated Farming Systems

3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated and soil amendments.

As indicated earlier, rainfed production is the system in the two islands. However, irrigation is gradually becoming important due to erratic rainfall and other problems associated with climate change. Drip irrigation is the most common type of irrigation practiced in both islands (76.5% and 100% in Santo Antao and Maio of our survey respondents respectively), even though some farmers (17.6%) undertake surface water irrigation in Santo Antao Island (Table 3.20). The types of crops grown under irrigation (in order of the most cultivated) in the two islands are indicated in Table 3.21.

Table 3.20: Types of irrigation undertaken

Irrigation types	Santo Antao		Maio	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	3	17.6	0	0.0
Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	13	76.5	14	100.0
Other	1	5.9	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 3.21: Types of crops grown under irrigation

Type of crops Irrigated	Santo Antao		Type of crops Irrigated	Maio	
	Freq	% Freq		Freq	% Freq
Carrots	10	22.2	Sweet potato	14	29.2
Onions	8	17.8	Onions	12	25.0
Tomatoes	7	15.6	Cassava	4	8.3
Sweet potato	5	11.1	Tomatoes	4	8.3
Sugarcane	3	6.7	Potato (English/Irish)	2	4.2
Potato (English/Irish)	2	4.4	Carrots	2	4.2
Leafy vegetables (local)	2	4.4	Pepper	2	4.2
Pepper	2	4.4	Sugarcane	2	4.2
Maize	1	2.2	Maize	1	2.1
Cassava	1	2.2	Beetroot	1	2.1
Beetroot	1	2.2	Leafy vegetables (local)	1	2.1
Banana	1	2.2	Kenaf	1	2.1
Other	1	2.2	Mango	1	2.1
Pumpkin	1	2.2	Pawpaw/Papaya	1	2.1
Total	45	100.0	Total	48	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.3.2 Soil amendments in irrigated plots and perceived success of irrigation

Table 3.22 gives information on the types of soil amendments undertaken in irrigated plots. None of the irrigators used only inorganic fertilizers. In both Santo Antao and Maio, they either used a mixture of organic and inorganic fertilizers or only organic fertilizers. That is an indication of the importance attached to organic matter in irrigated agriculture, and very good indication of high possibility of success of agroecological practices.

Table 3.22: Types of soil amendments used in irrigated plots.

Island	Type of Irrigation	Type of Soil Amendments			
		Only organic fertilizers		Inorganic and organic fertilizers	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	3	100.0
	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	4	30.8	9	69.2
	Other	5	31.3	11	68.8
Maio	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	12	85.7	2	14.3
Total		21	45.7	25	54.3

Source: Field survey, 2023

Irrigators were asked to indicate the extent of success of the irrigated agriculture they were undertaking. Table 3.23 are the responses. All of them indicated some level of success (that is somehow successful, successful and very successful), even though all felt there is need for improvements, especially given the prevailing climate change situation. The limited availability of water is a major problem in several places in the Islands. Drip irrigation is particularly indicated to be a successful irrigation system and needs to be promoted for minimal use of water and as a climate change adaptation measure.

Tables 3.23: Perceived degree of success of irrigation in islands

Island	Type of Irrigation	Degree of Success					
		Somehow successful		Successful		Very successful	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	2	50.0	2	50.0	0	0.0
	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	2	15.48	11	84.6	0	0.0
	Other	11	68.8	5	31.3	1	
Maio	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	14	100	0	0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.3.2 Irrigation constraints

Irrigated agriculture in Santo Antao and Maio faces several constraints as given in Table 3.24. Scarcity of water is the most mentioned constraint as indicated in the table.

Table 3.24: Irrigation constraints

Islands	Type of Irrigation	Constraints	Freq	% Freq
Santo Antao	Smallholder surface water irrigation	Poor access to irrigated land	1	33.3
		Water shortages	2	66.7
	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	Poor access to irrigated land	2	10.5
		Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	2	10.5
		High costs of inputs	2	10.5
		Inadequate access to markets	3	15.8
		Water shortages	10	52.6
Maio	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers, etc)	5	19.2
		High costs of inputs	4	15.4
		Inadequate access to markets for the sale of produce	4	15.4
		Water shortages	13	50.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

CHAPTER 4

OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS

4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources

4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale

The main sources of income to rural households in Cape Verde are from agriculture including crop farming, fishing, and livestock rearing. Other sources of income may include tourism, transportation, petty trading, agri-food processing (e.g. liqueurs), food vending (rabidantes), as well as salaried work, among others. The nature of small farming activities in the study area makes it difficult to adequately estimate household income. As seen in Tables 3.1 and 3.2, most plots consist of crop mixtures, ranging from two to as many as six. To comprehensively estimate the income from a plot, the value of all the crops harvested in the plot must be determined. Such information is difficult to obtain from farmers through recall interviews. Attempts were, however, made to obtain some idea of the income earned from arable crop farming, which is the main occupation of most household members in the study area, by estimating the value of two main crops in crop mixture plots in each of the plots. In the case of sole crop plots, the value of the sole crop is estimated. It is the total harvested quantity that is valued. The prices are those the farmers gave at the time of the interviews. This explanation is to indicate that caution is required in drawing conclusions from the results since changes, even small changes, in prices and quantities harvested can give drastically different results. Also, what is presented in each case is gross income and not gross margin. Cost of production was not estimated because such information from recall by small farmers is not reliable and will not serve much purpose in this study. Income from livestock production was also not estimated for the same reason of unreliability of the information given by farmers. Table 4.1 gives the procedure and formula used for the estimation of household crop income.

Table 4.1: Method of estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
					P _{A1}	P _{B1}	
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	$(Q_{A1} \times P_{A1}) + (Q_{B1} \times P_{B1})$
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	$(Q_{A2} \times P_{A2}) + (Q_{B2} \times P_{B2})$
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{A_i}	Q _{B_i}	P _{A_i}	P _{B_i}	$(Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i})$
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							$N \sum_{i=1}^n ((Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i}))$
A1 = crop A from plot 1; Q _{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P _{A1} = Price of A1 B1 = crop B from plot 1; Q _{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P _{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A _i = Crop A from plot i; Q _{A_i} = A _i harvested quantity; P _{A_i} = Price of A _i etc.							

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 4.2 gives the estimated average annual incomes obtained by households from crops (using the equation given in Table 4.1)². On average, household crop produce was estimated to be worth 599,521.94 CVE in Santo Antao and 456,542.86 CVE in Maio. The estimated amount for the women was only 150,000 CVE. It should be noted that in Maio there are only household plots (i.e. no individual men or women plots).

Table 4.2: Value of crop output per household*

Island	Average value of harvested crops in men headed HHs in 2022 season (CVE)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 102.04 CVE)	Average value of harvested crops per in women headed HHs in 2022 season (CVE)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 102.04 CVE)
Santo Antao	599,521.94	5,875.36	150,000.00	1,470,01
Maio	456,542.86	4,474.16	-	-
Both Islands (income per HH)	528,032.40	5,174.76	-	-

*See Appendix 1 for details of crop output value estimations.

Source: Field survey, 2023

It is obvious from Table 4.2 that the income received from arable crop farming by households is small. If it is assumed that half of the value stated was covered by the cost of production, it means the men headed households obtained less than 3,000 Euros from their main farms. The women's case is even worse off. The main reason for the very low value of their farm produce is their relatively small farm plots. While for men headed HHs in Santo Antao, the area of production per HH was 4,483m², that of the women headed HHs was only 1,273m² (see Tables 2.12 and 2.13). That means the incomes per unit area are about 1.31 Euros/m² for men and 1.15 Euros/m² for women in Santo Antao. It is obvious that the production cost per square meter will be more than the Escudo equivalents of 1.31 Euros and 1.15 Euros, and that the farmers are making losses. Interventions must aim at increasing productivity (output per unit area) substantially.

It is not the total quantities of crops produced that are sold. Relatively large proportions are usually reserved for home consumption (and other home uses such as livestock feed and seed) and some are given out as gifts to relatives and others. Men and women respondents were asked to give the proportions that are usually reserved for home consumption and given out as gifts. The assumption is that the proportion left after the two allocations is what is sold. That information is presented in Table 4.3.

Men and women in Santo Antao Island estimated that about 38.1% and 32.2% respectively of their farm produce is for home consumption and other home uses. The two estimates have quite high standard deviations (Table 4.3) indicating that there is some divergence in opinions. In Maio, the men's estimate is only 11% with a relatively low standard deviation suggesting that

² See Appendix 1 for details of estimations of values of crop output.

there is much greater agreement on the estimate. It is surprising the estimates given are less than 50%. The impression has always been that small scale farmers produce for subsistence but the information here does not support that view. The very low estimate for home consumption in Maio needs further investigation to know why it is so. Over 80% of the produce is sold. It could be partly because production in Maio is largely by irrigation and most irrigated produce is sold.

Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold according men and women in Santo Antao and Maio

Item	Santo Antao		Maio	
	HHH (men) Mean (Std Dev)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std Dev.)	HHH (men) Mean (Std. Dev.)	WiHH Mean (Std. Dev.)
Proportion (%) normally left for home consumption and other home uses (e.g. livestock, seed etc.) (A)	38.10 (36.47)	32.29 (32.78)	11.64 (8.42)	-
Proportion (%) quantity normally given out to relatives, friends etc. (as gifts) (B)	9.57 (9.01)	7.00 (10.95)	6.63 (4.03)	-
Proportion (%) normally sold (100- (A+B))	52.33	60.71	81.73	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 4.3 also indicates that between 7% and 10% of the produce is usually given out as gifts which means over 50% of the farm produce in the two islands of Cape Verde are sold. It is not that the allocation for home consumption is adequate for household members, but they require cash income to settle debts and for other necessary expenditures.

4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources

Almost all households in the islands obtain income from other sources than their farms. Those are generally referred to as non-farm income sources. It is, however, sometimes difficult to differentiate between some farm and non-farm activities in farming communities. Should the sale of labour, the picking and sale of semi-wild fruits (such as sheanuts, dawadawa, etc.), food processing etc. be classified non-farm activities? For the purposes of this study all the examples given are classified as non-farm activities and are thus non-farm income sources. Table 4.4 gives estimates of non-farm incomes for both men and women in Santo Antao and for men in Maio.

Food processing and petty trading/food vending are very good sources of income to men HHs in Santo Antao, while sale of labour is the main 'non-farm' source of income for women. In Maio charcoal production is the main non-farm source of income (Table 4.4). The respondents to the questions from which these figures are obtained were quite few. Indeed, those with

‘means’ without stated standard deviations were one respondent each. It is thus necessary to interpret the results presented with utmost caution. The result in Table 4.4 implies that only food processing earns about 4,655 Euros per annum, almost equal to the value of crops produced. The food processors are however few and are not the small farmers being considered here so what is presented is not non-farm income meant to complement HH farm income. It is however good to know that food processing is a very lucrative business adventure. Sale of labour is a major non-farm source of income for men and women in Santo Antao and men in Maio. The amount obtained, about 40,000 CVE (392 Euros) and 163,333 CVE (1,600 Euros) per annum for men and women respectively in Santo Antao about 50,000 CVE (490 Euros) per annum for men in Maio is, however, too small. Charcoal production, which is an anti-environmental practice, is also a major non-farm income source in Maio. About 180,000 CVE (about 1,764 Euros) per annum or 147 Euros per month are obtained by a household on the average. This very meagre amount does not justify the destruction of the forest in Maio. An alternative income source that will prevent charcoal production must be found.

Table 4.4: Non-farm income (Cape Verde Escudo - CVE) of HHHs (men) and WiHH (women) – Santo Antao and Maio (1 Euro = 102.04 CVE)

Non-farm income source	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Santo Antao – HHH (men)				
Food processing	475,000.00	35,355.339	450000	500000
Petty trading/food vending	204,000.00	-	204000	204000
Sale of labour	40,000.00	39,528.471	5000	100000
Pension	72,000.00	-	72000	72000
Salary	27,000.00	-	27000	27000
Santo Antao - WiHH (Women)				
Sale of labour	163,333.33	100,166.528	50000	240000
Salary	93,000.00	123,036.580	6000	180000
Maio – HHH (men)				
Charcoal production	180,000.00	-	180000	180000
Sale of labour	50,000.00	-	50000	50000

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Quantitative information as given above, especially from a relatively small sample, cannot capture a lot of information. It is thus important to supplement most of the quantitative information with qualitative information. A method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies³, was used to determine the relative importance of the non-farm income sources to the farmers. Respondents were asked to rank the sources of income from 1 to 5, 1 being the most important and 5 the least important. The frequencies obtained were then weighted and scores obtained for the source of income. The weighted scores are presented in Figure 4.1. See Appendix 2 for the

³ See Appendix 2 for details of the method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies.

methods used to obtain the weighted scores. The weighted scores give farmers' perception of the importance of the income sources based on their experience over time.

In the case of men in Santo Antao Island, sale of labour, petty trading/food vending, food processing and salaried work (formal employment) are the main important sources of non-farm income. In Maio Island, sale of labour, salary and charcoal production are the main non-farm sources of income for men (Figure 4.1). For the women in Santo Antao, it is sale of labour, food processing and some unspecified activities that are the main sources of non-farm activities (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.1: Relative importance of non-farm sources according to HHHs - Santo Antao and Maio

Figure 4.2: Relative importance of non-farm income sources according to WiHHs – Santo Antao

4.2 Expenditure by Households

Estimation of income of households is difficult as discussed above. It is even more difficult for households to estimate their expenditures for the year. Some estimates of expenditures were however, obtained from respondents. Survey experience and exercise of patience are usually what is use to obtain some of this information, and even with that gaps are inevitable and accuracy of the information can be a challenge. There are thus likely to be significant gaps in the information on household expenditure as presented in Table 4.5 and accuracy of the information cannot be guaranteed. It is still good information because it largely provides information on the relative expenditure on the different households' needs and requirements.

Table 4.5: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023)

Santo Antao			Maio	
Expenditure Item	HHH	WiHH	Expenditure Item	HHH
	Amount per HH per annum (CVE)			Amount per HH per annum
Livestock inputs	52,000.00	-	Transportation (for farm activities)	66,000.00
Transportation (general)	29,426.70	86,050.00	Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	58,000.00
Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	24,100.00	92,500.00	Transportation (general)	50,000.00
Schooling expenses	21,456.00	19,200.00	Food (grain)	11,000.00
Food (grain)	18,733.30	45,175.00	Irrigation water charges	8,333.30
Soup ingredients	17,066.70	19,200.00	Other (Specify)	8,000.00
Meat and dairy	12,800.00	27,500.00	Livestock inputs	1,333.30
Transportation (for farm activities)	12,200.00	-	Farm inputs	-
Other (other products not listed)	7,800.00	52,966.70	Orthodox health care for HH members	-
Farm inputs	6,033.30	-	Traditional health care for HH members	-
Irrigation water charges	3,456.00	-	Schooling expenses	-
Orthodox health care for HH members	2,000.00	-	Amenities	-
Clothing	1,333.30	6,000.00	Soup ingredients	-
Amenities	1,333.30	-	Meat and dairy	-
Traditional health care for HH members	-	-	Clothing	-
Remittances/Gifts	-	-	Remittances/Gifts	-
Firewood/Charcoal	-	-	Firewood/Charcoal	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 4.5 shows the differences between expenditures by men and women in Santo Antao and men in Maio. While men expend a lot of money on livestock inputs, the women did not even consider those in the survey. The women spent considerable amounts on transportation, food grains and school expenses of their children (Table 4.5). The table gives considerable information on relative expenditures by both men and women in Santo Antao and men in Maio. It is surprising both men and women did not indicate any expenditure on traditional healthcare and firewood/charcoal.

The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies was used to determine respondents' perceived relative importance of HH expenditure items (HH items requiring use of cash to obtain). The method comprehensively obtains respondents' choices using a scale of 5. The information is given in Figure 4.3 for men HHs in Santo Antao and Maio. The ranks, frequencies and weighted scores computation are given in Appendix 3. The qualitative information of Figure 4.3 complements the quantitative information in Table 4.5. It indeed fills gaps in Table 4.5. Expenditure on food grains, land preparation and irrigation water charges are for example as prominent in Table 4.5 as seen in Figure 4.3. Also while expenditure on farm inputs, school expenses and amenities for Maio are not captured in Table 4.5, they are shown be prominent in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Relative importance of HH expenditure items

CHAPTER 5

HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY, DIETARY DIVERSITY AND WEALTH AND POVERTY PERCEPTIONS

5.1 Household Food Security

5.1.1 Shortages of cultivated crops by months in 2021 and 2022

Table 5.1 indicates that there have been food shortages in all months of 2021 and 2022 in both islands. The spread of the data is quite even such that it may be difficult to claim that food shortages are predominant in particular months. As indicated earlier, most of the cultivation is on small plots while there are limited non-farm sources of income. Most livelihood activities are therefore carried out all year round, and depending on one's source of income, one can run out of food at any time of the year. It is clear from Table 5.1 that household food production cannot ensure household food security. Food, including basic food stuffs, must be purchased all year round.

Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022

Shortage of Cultivated Food	Santo Antao		Maio	
	HHHs		HHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
January	8 (8.2)	6 (5.5)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)
February	7 (7.1)	8 (7.3)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)
March	8 (8.2)	8 (7.3)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
April	8 (8.2)	11 (10)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
May	8 (8.2)	11 (10)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
June	9 (9.2)	12 (10.9)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)
July	9 (9.2)	12 (10.9)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)
August	9 (9.2)	12 (10.9)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
September	9 (9.2)	11 (10)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
October	9 (9.2)	8 (7.3)	3 (12.5)	2 (11.1)
November	7 (7.1)	6 (5.5)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)
December	7 (7.1)	5 (4.5)	1 (4.2)	1 (5.6)

Source: Field survey, May 2023

5.1.2 Sources of income for food purchases

The sources of income for food purchases in both Islands are many and varied, including income from salaried work, sale of cash crops, sale of food crops, sale of animals, remittances from relatives, petty trading, credit (cash or in-kind), businesses (of all kinds), and sale of labour among others. Interestingly, Table 5.2 shows that the primary source of income for food purchases is through sale of food crops and cash crops. That means farm households sell their food produce only to buy them and others later. They have to sell to meet several cash obligations but have to buy they run short of foodstuffs. Also, no farmer can produce all the crops it requires they have to sell some of their produce (cash or food crops) to buy other necessary food items.

Table 5.2: Sources of income for food purchase.

Source of Income	Santo Antao		Maio	
	HHHs		HHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
Income from salaried work	4 (11.4)	5 (14.3)	5 (15.2)	4 (12.5)
Sale of cash crops	9 (25.7)	9 (25.7)	9 (27.3)	9 (28.1)
Sale of food crops	11(31.4)	10 (28.6)	14 (42.4)	13 (40.6)
Sale of animals	2 (5.7)	3 (8.6)	3 (9.1)	3 (9.1)
Remittances from relatives	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Petty trading	1(2.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.1)
Credit (cash or in-kind)	1(2.9)	1(2.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Other - Sale of labour	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Other	7 (20.0)	7 (20.0)	2 (6.1)	2 (6.3)
Business	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

Source: Field survey, May 2023

5.2 Household Dietary Diversity

5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day- HHH

All the household heads (men) in Santo Antao had consumed food made from grains or cereals (primarily maize and rice-based) and other foods, such as condiments, in the day before the interview. Nearly all of them also consumed foods made from legumes (beans and/or groundnuts), oil, fat, or butter; and sugar or honey (Table 5.3). At least a little over two-thirds of the household heads in Santo Antao consumed eggs and dairy products, while more than half consumed starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, vegetables and meat and organs. Fruit is the least consumed food group. In Santo Antao, a considerable proportion (63%) of the interviewed household heads exhibited high dietary diversity, with 4% showing low dietary diversity. For Maio, all the household heads (men) consumed food made from seafood, especially fish and oil, fat, or butter (Table 5.3.). Nearly all of them also consumed foods made from grains or cereals, condiments, and sugar or honey. At least two-thirds of the household heads in Maio consume vegetables and eggs, while a little over two-thirds consume tuber-based diets, dairy, and meat and organs. Fruit is the least consumed food group. In Maio, a considerable proportion (67%) of the interviewed household heads exhibited high dietary diversity, with no one showing low dietary diversity.

The dietary habits of household heads in both Santo Antao and Maio demonstrate high nutritional diversity, encompassing grains, legumes, vegetables, and various protein sources like meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy products. This diversity suggests access to essential nutrients crucial for overall health. Differences in dietary habits between the two islands reflect regional variations in food availability, cultural preferences, and traditional diets. For example, Maio's coastal location influences higher seafood consumption, while Santo Antao's preference for meat and organs may stem from cultural and historical factors. While diverse diets have positive health implications, disparities such as low fruit consumption in both islands may indicate potential nutritional deficiencies and health risks requiring attention.

Table 5.3: Household head Dietary Diversity (HDDS) Cape Verde

	Santo Antao N = 26		Maio N = 15	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	26	100.0	14	93.3
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	15	57.7	12	80.0
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	14	53.8	10	66.7
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	6	24.0	7	46.7
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	16	64.0	11	73.3
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	18	72.0	10	66.7
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, cat fish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	13	50.0	15	100.0
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	23	88.5	12	80.0
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	18	72.0	11	73.3
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	24	96.0	15	100.0
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	22	91.7	13	86.7
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, baobab?	25	100.0	14	93.3
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	1	4.2	0	0.0
Moderate	8	33.3	5	33.3
High	15	62.5	10	66.7

Source: Field survey, 2023

5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHH

All the women in households in Santo Antao had consumed food made from legumes (beans/groundnuts), sugar, or honey, as well as other food condiments such as coffee, on the day before the interview. Nearly all of them also consumed foods made from cereals/grains, and oil, fat, or butter (Table 5.4). At least a little over two-thirds of the women in households in Santo Antao consumed eggs and dairy products, while more than half (62.5% each) consumed starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, vegetables, seafood (e.g., fish), and meat and organs. Fruit is the least consumed food group. In Santo Antao, a considerable

proportion (63%) of the interviewed women in households exhibited high dietary diversity, while 6.3% showed low dietary diversity. The dietary habits of women in Santo Antao appear to be relatively diverse, encompassing legumes, cereals/grains, oils/fats, dairy products, vegetables, seafood, and meat/organs. However, the low consumption of fruits. It was reported as the least consumed food group. That raises concerns regarding fruit availability and accessibility in the island by the people. Given that fruits are crucial sources of vitamins, fiber, and antioxidants, their limited intake may signal potential nutritional deficiencies among women interviewed in Santo Antao.

Table 5.4 Women in household Dietary Diversity (WiHDDS) Cape Verde

	Santo Antao	
	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	15	93.8
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	10	62.5
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	10	62.5
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, pawpaw, Dimbu etc	3	18.8
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	10	62.5
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	12	75.0
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, cat fish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	10	62.5
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	16	100.0
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	11	68.8
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	15	93.8
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	16	100.0
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, baobab?	16	100.0
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>		
Low	1	6.3
Moderate	5	31.3
High	10	62.5

Source: Field survey, 2023

5.2.3 Household heads and women in household comparison in Santo Antao Island

While there are similarities in the dietary habits of men and women in Santo Antao, women showed a slightly broader range of food consumption, particularly by including more seafood, meat, and organs in their diets. Both men and women in Santo Antao exhibited similar consumption patterns regarding legumes, cereals/grains, oil, fat, butter, eggs, and dairy products. Women displayed slightly greater dietary diversity, as they also consumed seafood, meat, and organs compared to men. Fruit was the least consumed food group for both genders. Nevertheless, more women than men exhibit low dietary diversity on Santo Antao Island.

5.3 Wealth and Poverty Status of Households and Communities (To be completed)

The general perception of the communities in both Islands is that the people are averagely poor. They admit that there is always food available to families but the perception of being poor arises mainly from the lack of employment for the youth. Other reasons peculiar to some rural communities include:

- Lack of access to health care and sanitation at the local level.
- Unprofitable livelihoods activities e.g fishing.
- Poor housing facilities e.g some families have bathrooms, but some with no kitchen.
- Lack of roads leading to the isolation and distancing of communities from public institutions and authorities.
- Low literacy and financial resources that lead to a very low level of economic dynamism and entrepreneurship.
- Gender inequality because there are few empowered women. Many women heads of households end up being vulnerable. While they are looking after their homes, the men are mostly out on the streets with more opportunities to work and study.
- Increased population without corresponding economic growth.

CHAPTER 6

HOUSEHOLD RESOURCE AND USE

6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time

Household lands are important in farming crops and raising livestock. They therefore play an important role in food security. The dynamics between the area cultivated and fallow areas give an indication of agricultural practices that may be feasible in the area. It will, for example, dictate whether a farmer can practice fallowing and for how long a farm may be left under fallow.

Cultivated and uncultivated land areas per household in Santo Antao and Maio are as given in Table 6.1. What the table shows is that there is no land for cultivation. Even the virgin land, which is the largest of the three categories of land is less than one acre. Men's average cultivated land in Santo Antao is about half an acre, and for the men it is less than 0.2 acres. In the case of Maio the cultivated land per HH is about 11 acres and land under fallow is about 2 acres per HH. The limited land for cultivation in the Islands demand that very innovative agroecological practices are created which will ensure that "more (output) from little".

Table 6.1: Availability and use of household lands in Santo Antao and Maio Islands

	Owned land (m ²)		Land not owned (m ²)		Land not owned but accessible for farming (m ²)	
	Mean area	Std. Dev.	Mean area	Std. Dev.	Mean area	Std. Dev.
Santo Antao Island – Men (HHH)						
Cultivated land	2,165.0	1,995.3	3,217.9	2,227.4	-	-
Fallow land	1,656.7	1,468.6	0.0	-	2,000	.
Virgin land	3,500.0	3,535.5	0.0	-	-	-
Santo Antao Island – Women (WiHH)						
Cultivated land	756.7	650.1	700.0	.		
Fallow land						
Virgin land	1250.0	.				
Maio Island – Men (HHH)						
Cultivated land	43,750.0	49,479.4	2500.0	-	-	-
Fallow land	7,500.0	7,071.1	0.0		-	-
Virgin land	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-

Source: Field survey, May 2023

When farmers were asked if they could obtain more land for cultivation, 65.2% and 63.6% of men in Santo Antao and Maio respectively said no, while 85.7% of the women in Santo Antao also said no (Table 6.2). That buttresses the carious nature of the land availability problem in the islands and the importance of agroecological practices in the islands. According to those who said they have the possibility of cropping more land in Santo Antao, sharecropping is what is possible. In Maio, however, the young farmers felt they can inherit and/or borrow land to farm. The women in Santo Antao do not see any possibility of acquiring more land for farming (Table 6.3)

Table 6.2: Availability of additional land for farming

	Santo Antao				Maio			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HHH	8	34.8	15	65.2	4	36.4	7	63.6
WiHH	1	14.3	6	85.7	0	0.00	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 6.3: Source of extra land for farming in Santo Antao and Maio

	Santo Antao		Maio	
	HH	WIHH	HH	WIHH
	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Inheritance;	1	0	1	0
Borrowed (Free)	0	0	1	0
Share cropping	3	1	0	0
Others	4	0	2	0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

6.2 Reasons for Yields Change Over Time

Yields change over time acknowledges the dynamic aspect of agricultural productivity, involving fluctuations in both the quantity and quality of crops or livestock over various periods. This variability is influenced by factors such as environmental conditions, technological improvements, management practices, and socio-economic factors. Yields, whether in terms of crop output per acre or livestock productivity, seldom remain consistent. The following findings on increases or decreases specifically relate to information obtained from household heads (HHs) and women in households (WiHHs) on Santo Antao and Maio Islands.

In Santo Antao Island, the rise in yields of some crops over the past 5 years for men is attributed to good land management, adequate use of fertilizer/manure, fertile soils, and effective crop management as indicated in Figure 6.1. In Maio, the farmers did not indicate any increase in yields, but rather decreased yields.

Figure 6.1: Household heads reasons for increase in yields over time by in Santo Antao

In Santo Antao Island, women experienced increase in yields of some crops due to two main factors: effective land management and sufficient use of fertilizer and/or manure for soil amendment (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2 WiHH reasons for increase in yields over time – Santo Antao

The decline in yields of some crops in the Islands can stem from a variety of factors. In Santo Antao Island, HHHs identify unreliable rainfall and the presence of pests and diseases as primary reasons for the decrease in yields over time. Conversely, in Maio, factors contributing to yield reduction are associated with unreliable rainfall, prevalence of pests and diseases, poor soil fertility, reduced use of inputs, financial constraints, and labour shortages (Figure 6.3). For the women in Santo Antao, unreliable rainfall, pests and diseases, poor soil fertility, and weed management are the main reasons for decrease in yields over time in Santo Antao (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.3 HHHs reasons for decrease in yields over time by island

Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields over time in Santo Antao

While men and women in Santo Antao and Maio islands share common concerns regarding yield decline, women in Santo Antao provide a more comprehensive perspective, emphasizing additional factors such as poor soil fertility and weed management. This highlights the importance of gender-sensitive approaches to agricultural development that address the specific needs and challenges faced by women farmers.

The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies, as explained in other sections and in the Appendix, was used to obtain the weighted scores presented in the figures above. The method comprehensively obtains respondents' choices using a scale of 5.

CHAPTER 7

AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES

7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices

Adopting ecologically sound farming practices is paramount for the sustainability of agriculture. This section delves into the multifaceted sphere of sustainable agriculture, focusing on crucial elements such as the knowledge and use of agroecological practices. It discusses the determining factors steering the use of these practices, emphasizing their seamless integration into farming systems. Furthermore, the section explores the types and uses of agro-wastes, as well as the quantities generated by households, as integral components in nurturing a holistic and environmentally conscious approach to agriculture.

Agroecological practices play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable agriculture, promoting environmentally friendly and resilient farming systems. Assessing the awareness and usage of these practices on both the Santo Antao and Maio Islands, as well as perceptive differences between men and women at the gender level, is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of sustainable farming initiatives.

7.1.1 Agroecological awareness and practices in Santo Antao Island

In the Santo Antao Island, men (household heads) are primarily aware of and mentioned 13 agroecological practices. Key among them is mulching, farmyard manure, drip irrigation, crop rotation, fallow, and stone bunds/ terracing. Specifically, 34.6% of men are aware of mulching while 26.9% and 19.2% respectively are aware of farmyard manure and drip irrigation. Approximately 8% each are aware of crop rotation, fallow, and stone bunds/ terracing (Table 7.1). The use of the practices in the 2022 season and 5 years ago were, however, lower as given in the Table.

Some practices, such as mulching and the use of farmyard manure, show higher awareness and utilization rates compared to others like crop rotation, fallow, and stone bunds/terracing. This may indicate varying levels of perceived benefits and ease of implementation among farmers. For instance, farmyard manure and stone bunds/terracing are regarded as traditional practices during the key informant interviews and focus group discussions. Crop rotation and intercropping were singled out because of their benefits. 'Crop rotation and intercropping both promote diversity and reduce soil depletion,' mentioned one key informant. Regarding agroforestry, one key informant indicated that although some male farmers may be aware of it, its usage may be low due to a lack of tree nurseries or small plot sizes, making it difficult to practice. Others, including key informants, opined that the information on agroforestry in the survey reflects reality, as it used to be a practice from the olden days. Regarding integrated crop-livestock management, as indicated during the key informant interviews, much of it is not practiced because most livestock are confined.

For women on Santo Antao Island, the mentioned agroecological practices include farmyard manure, mulching, crop rotation, rainwater harvesting, and drip irrigation (Table 7.2). Among these practices, farmyard manure is the most recognized, with 35.3% of women being aware of it. About 11.8% of the women mentioned that they are aware of mulching, crop rotation, and rainwater harvesting as agroecological practices. About 5.9% indicated awareness of drip irrigation. Though there was some level of awareness among women on Santo Antao Island, mulching, crop rotation, rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai, etc.), and drip irrigation, the use has been minimal. According to key informants, mulching for example, is seldom used by women, due to the millipede plague, even though they are aware of its effectiveness in controlling weeds and increasing production.

Table 7.1: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Santo Antao Island

Agroecological practices	Men (HHHs) (N = 26)					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Mulching	9	34.6	7	26.9	6	23.1
Farmyard manure	7	26.9	7	26.9	5	19.2
Drip Irrigation	5	19.2	4	15.4	2	7.7
Crop rotation	2	7.7	2	7.7	2	7.7
Fallow	2	7.7	2	7.7	1	3.8
Stone bunds/ terracing	2	7.7	2	7.7	2	7.7
Soil bunds	1	3.8	1	3.8	1	3.8
Improved water management	1	3.8	1	3.8	1	3.8
Early maturing /drought resistant varieties	1	3.8	1	3.8	0	0.0
Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai etc)	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Green manure e.g. Mucuna	1	3.8	1	3.8	1	3.8
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	1	3.8	1	3.8	1	3.8
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	1	3.8	1	3.8	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 7.2: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Santo Antao Island

Agroecological practices	Women (WiHHs) (N = 17)					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Mulching	2	11.8	0	0.0	1	5.9
Farmyard manure	6	35.3	1	5.9	1	5.9
Drip Irrigation	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	2	11.8	0	0.0	1	5.9
Fallow	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Stone bunds/ terracing	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Soil bunds	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Improved water management	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Early maturing /drought resistant varieties	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai etc)	2	11.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Green manure e.g. Mucuna	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The awareness levels for different practices in Santo Antao Island among men and women show notable differences. Some practices, like mulching and farmyard manure, demonstrate relatively high utilization rates, while others are rarely used. Men and women exhibit different levels of awareness for specific practices, with women showing higher awareness of farmyard manure compared to men. Men demonstrate varied utilization rates for different practices, whereas women seem to have higher utilization rates for farmyard manure, mulching, and crop rotation. The varying levels of awareness and utilization may indicate differing perceptions of benefits and ease of implementation among men and women.

7.1.2 Agroecological awareness and practices in Maio Island

In Maio Island, men (household heads) are primarily aware of and mentioned various agroecological practices, including farmyard manure, drip irrigation, mulching, and crop rotation. Specifically, 80.0%, 13.3%, 6.7% and 6.7% of men are aware of farmyard manure, drip irrigation, mulching and crop rotation respectively (Table 7.3). The agroecological practices mentioned in the survey, align with the information provided in the focus group discussions and key informant interviews.

With respect to use of these agroecological practices, 80% of Maio men used farmyard manure in the 2022 season as well as 5 years ago, indicating that it had been a normal practice over time. Farmyard manure is mostly used by farmers practicing irrigation, according to the key informant interviews. Similarly, the men who indicated awareness of drip irrigation and mulching, used them in the 2022 season. Crop rotation and mulching, as confirmed by key informants, are not regular practices implemented by farmers, which is the reason for the low

percentage usage. Contrary to the survey, agroforestry and intercropping were mentioned as practices commonly used by men during the key informant interviews.

Table 7.3: HHHs agroecological technologies in Maio Island (N = 15)

Agroecological practices	Men (HHHs)					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Farmyard manure	12	80.0	12	80.0	12	80.0
Drip Irrigation	2	13.3	2	13.3	2	13.3
Mulching	1	6.7	1	6.7	0	0.0
Crop rotation	1	6.7	1	6.7	1	6.7

Source: Field survey, May 2023

It can be concluded that both Santo Antao and Maio islands farmers exhibit awareness and utilization of agroecological practices. While Maio Island emphasizes a narrower range of practices with higher utilization rates, Santo Antao Island presents a broader spectrum of practices with lower utilization rates, except for farmyard manure and mulching among men.

7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices

The use of agroecological practices is influenced by various factors, and understanding these elements is crucial for promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural approaches. Tables 7.4, 7.5, 7.6 and 7.7 show key factors that determine the use of the main agroecological practices, as well as differences in use between genders in Santo Antao and Maio. The factors influencing men's use of mulching and farmyard manure in Santo Antao are associated with the availability of inputs (43% each) necessary for carrying out these practices, improving soil quality (31% and 38%) due to the prevalence of infertile land, the technical capability of household heads to implement these practices, and high expectations of benefits. For most men, mulching technology is perceived as low cost (100%) and of low risk (50%). While women in households have similar reasons for using mulching, particularly the expected high benefits, and its application on infertile lands, the percentages differ from those of men. Both men and women anticipate the high benefits of mulching, with 20% of women and 25% of men; 50% of women perceive its usage on infertile lands while only 25% of men share this perception. Additionally, factors determining women's use of crop rotation and farmyard manure include their perception of soil improvement (20% and 80%), anticipated benefits (40% and 20%), technical capacity to implement these practices (50% each), and their low-risk nature (50% each). Furthermore, women's usage of farmyard manure is influenced by the availability of inputs.

Tables 7.4: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in Santo Antao

	Improves the soil		High expected benefits		Availability of inputs		Technically capable		Low risk	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Household heads (men)										
Mulching	5	31.3	2	25.0	3	42.9	1	16.7	3	50.0
Farmyard manure	6	37.5	1	12.5	3	42.9	2	33.3	0	0.0
Women in household										
Mulching	0	0.0	1	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	1	20.0	2	40.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	1	50.0
Farmyard manure	4	80.0	1	20.0	2	100.0	1	50.0	1	50.0

Note: Percentages are of those who answered the specific questions not the survey sample size.

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Tables 7.5: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in Santo Antao

	Secure land tenure		Land is infertile		Low cost of technology		Saves water	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Household heads (men)								
Mulching	3	75.0	1	25.0	3	100.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	0	0.0	2	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Women in household								
Mulching	0	0.0	2	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	0	0.0	2	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Note: Percentages are of those who answered the specific questions not the survey sample size.

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Tables 7.6: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men in Maio island

	Improves the soil		Low risk		Low cost of technology		Availability of inputs	
	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Farmyard manure	12	92.3	7	87.5	6	100.0	4	100.0
Drip Irrigation	0	0.0	1	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	1	7.7	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Note: Percentages are of those who answered the specific questions not the survey sample size.

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Tables 7.7: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men in Maio island

	Low labour		Technically capable		Land is infertile	
	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Farmyard manure	3	100.0	2	100.0	2	100.0
Drip Irrigation	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Note: Percentages are of those who answered the specific questions not the survey sample size.

Source: Field survey, May 2023

In Santo Antao, both men and women prioritize soil improvement and anticipated benefits in their agricultural practices. However, there are notable differences in their perceptions and approaches, particularly regarding mulching and farmyard manure usage. Men tend to have higher percentages associated with anticipating benefits of mulching and perceiving its usage on infertile lands compared to women. Conversely, women exhibit a higher percentage for perceiving soil improvement and anticipated benefits for farmyard manure compared to men. Additionally, men perceive mulching technology as lower risk compared to women.

In Maio island, the factors influencing men's use of farmyard manure, drip irrigation, and crop rotation are mostly related. Various factors influence men's use of farmyard manure in Maio island. The determinants for the use of farmyard manure by men in Maio are associated with the low cost of technology (100%), availability of inputs (100%), low labour requirements (100%), technical capability (100%), suitability for infertile land (100%), soil improvement (92%), and low risk (88%). For drip irrigation, the primary determinant for use is its low risk, while for crop rotation, the main determinant for use is its ability to improve the soil.

7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes and Their Uses in Santo Antao and Maio Islands

Agro waste, which includes leftover plant materials, crop residues, and by-products, is generated as a by-product of farming and food processing. Tables 7.8, 7.9 and 7.10 present the various types of agro wastes and their applications in Santo Antao and Maio Islands, categorized by gender. Tables 7.8 and 7.9 show the various types of agro wastes and their uses by men (HHHs) and women (WiHHs) in Santo Antao. The types of agro waste used by men include stovers from cereals and animal manure. Among men in Santo Antao, cereal stovers serve as bedding or feed for livestock. About 25.0% of the HHHs incorporate animal manure into the soil, while about 12.0% sell the agro waste. Also 12% of HHHs indicated that animal manure is used for composting (Table 7.8). Table 7.9 illustrates that women in Santo Antao use agro waste, specifically for livestock feed or bedding. Cereal stovers and kitchen waste, in particular, serve as feed or bedding for livestock.

The use of cereal stovers and animal manure in livestock management and soil enrichment signifies sustainable agricultural practices. Cereal stovers as livestock bedding or feed enhance animal nutrition and health, potentially boosting productivity. Incorporating animal manure into the soil and composting improves soil fertility, water retention, and promotes beneficial microorganisms, vital for soil health. Utilizing agro waste reflects a commitment to resource recycling, reducing external inputs, and minimizing environmental impact. Selling surplus agro waste offers income generation opportunities, bolstering economic stability and livelihoods within the community. These practices collectively support sustainable agriculture, productivity, and household well-being.

Table 7.8A Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Santo Antao Island (N = 25)

	Uses of agro-waste					
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.0
Legumes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grasses	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Animal manure	5	20.0	3	12.0	1	4.0
Kitchen wastes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

**Table 7.8B Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Santo Antao Island (N = 25)
(Continued)**

	Uses of Agro-waste					
	Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Legumes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grasses	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Animal manure	0	0.0	3	12.0	0	0.0
Kitchen wastes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 7.9A Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Santo Antao Island (N = 17)

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro -waste					
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	5.9
Legumes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grasses	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Animal manure	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Kitchen wastes	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	11.8

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Both men and women in Santo Antao use agro waste for livestock management and soil enrichment. Men mainly utilize cereal stovers and animal manure, with almost a quarter integrating manure into the soil. Conversely, women primarily use kitchen waste and cereal stovers for livestock feed or bedding. During the focus group discussions, participants highlighted that crop residues from the fields are used as animal feed, but a significant amount is also wasted. Agricultural residues, such as straw, are often underutilized, with only a small portion being utilized for animal feed. Animals produce manure after consuming agricultural waste generated from the plots. Despite the abundance of agricultural waste, it is rarely utilized, with most of it being used for animal feed. Nevertheless, there are emerging examples of effective utilization. For example, sugar cane residue, which is abundant and often wasted, is now being used in agriculture to enrich the soil, sparking curiosity among farmers.

**Table 7.9B Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Santo Antao Island (N = 17)
(Continued)**

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro -waste					
	Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	Freq
Cereals (stovers)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Legumes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grasses	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Animal manure	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Kitchen wastes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Household heads in Maio indicated that animal manure, as a common form of agro waste, is incorporated into the soil (Table 7.10). The indication by 20.0% suggests that using animal manure as a form of fertilizer or soil amendment is a widespread practice among households in Maio. During the key informant interviews, some participants expressed their opinion that agricultural waste refers to the leaves of plants that are used as feed for animals after harvesting. They specifically mentioned straw scraps as examples of agricultural waste used for feeding animals even though it was not mentioned in the HH interviews.

The observations from Tables 7.8 to 7.10 highlight both the commonalities and subtle distinctions in the practices of utilizing agro waste between men and women in Santo Antao and Maio islands. In Santo Antao and Maio, agro waste is utilized for agricultural purposes, but the specific types of waste used, soil enrichment practices, and gender dynamics differ between the two regions. In Santo Antao, both men and women utilize agro waste, but their preferences vary. In Maio, the emphasis is on incorporating animal manure into the soil, suggesting a common practice among household heads.

Table 7.10 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Maio island

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro- waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/ bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Legumes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grasses	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Animal manure	5	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Kitchen wastes	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

CHAPTER 8

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES

8.1 Evidence of Climate Change

According to the household heads in Maio, the perceived evidence of climate change includes temperature increases, decreases in rainfall, increased drought, and the emergence of new insects (Figure 8.1). Although household heads in Santo Antao did not respond to the question in the survey, their perceived evidence of climate change, according to the FGDs and KIIs, is similar to that of Maio. These findings as reported by HHH in both islands suggest that climate change impacts are perceived similarly across different islands, emphasizing the widespread nature of these environmental changes in the islands.

Figure 8.1: Household heads perceived evidence of climate change

CHAPTER 9

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1 Summary

The islands of Santo Antao and Maio in Cape Verde, have the potential to increase food production significantly through agroecology. Already the use of agrochemicals is banned in Cape Verde and the people produce on very small plots because of scarcity of arable land. Also, most farmers in the Santo Antao and Maio (62.5% and 93.8% respectively) did not use inorganic fertilizers on their farms in 2022 farming season. Their food production is therefore largely agroecological. The average household farm holding in Santo Antao is 4,483m² (about 1.1 acre) and that in Maio is 19,413 m² (about 5 acres). Thus, intensive, sustainable and resilient production practices are the most suitable.

Main crops cultivated in the islands include maize, sweet potato, English/Irish potato, pigeon pea, cowpea, carrots, onions, tomatoes and others. Almost all the crops are grown in mixtures. Drip irrigation is a common practice in both islands. Labour scarcity, small farm sizes, erosion, and inadequate access to farming land and the destruction of tuber crops by centipedes are the main crop production constraints, while the main livestock production constraints are lack of feed and water during the dry season, diseases, poor housing, and theft.

The income obtained from crop production is generally very low, about 6,000 Euro equivalent per men headed HH per year and 1,470 Euro equivalent per women headed HH per year in Santo Antao, and about 4,500 Euro equivalent per HH per year in Maio. Over 50% of the food produced in the islands is sold even though it is not usually enough for the HHs.

Both men and women farmers are aware and practice several agroecological technologies. They include mulching, farmyard manure, drip irrigation, crop rotation, fallow, and stone bunds/terracing and rainwater harvesting.

9.2 Recommendations

1) Agroecological practices are generally common among farmers, and they involve the use local and community resources. What is required is improvements in the practices using modern science for greater productivity. The income per square meter of farmland (about 1.31 Euros/m² for men and 1.15 Euros/m² for women in Santo Antao) shows that farmers must be making huge losses from their crop production.

2) MACCLI (Manure-Agroforestry-Compost-Crop/Livestock Integration) agroecological technique fits the Cape Verde situation very well and should be adopted. It involves using all or some of the stated agroecological practices.

3) The present dependance on rainfed production is risky and getting worse because of climate change. Irrigated agriculture fits very well into the farming system of the Cape Verde but there

are various constraints, including limited access to groundwater. There is a need for agroecological solutions to rainwater and irrigation water management. Drip irrigation should be promoted due to its efficient water use but the cost is too high for the farmers and access to groundwater is a critical constraint. CIRAWA needs to use all its scientific knowledge to tackle this intricate problem.

4) Agroecological training is necessary especially for the youth and women and should be well planned and carried out in the islands. The youth in both islands and the women in Santo Antao have considerable farming experience and will most likely accept new ideas and co-created technologies.

5) Access to agricultural (both rainfed and irrigated) land is a big constraint especially for the women in Santo Antao. Given the structure of inheritance and family system in Santo Antao, there is need for government intervention in the agricultural land issue to help women households in their livelihood endeavours.

6) The tedium of production using the hoe is a problem. Small mechanical tools and equipment will help improve agricultural productivity especially by women and the youth.

7) The crop and animal diseases situation are quite acute and needs a solution. Agroecological solutions need to be found for the problems.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Estimation of household income from harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		1.2 Total quantity harvested (indicate units)		1.3 Price per unit (local currency)		1.4 Value of output (local currency)
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	$(Q_{A1} \times P_{A1}) + (Q_{B1} \times P_{B1})$
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	$(Q_{A2} \times P_{A2}) + (Q_{B2} \times P_{B2})$
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{A_i}	Q _{B_i}	P _{A_i}	P _{B_i}	$(Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i})$
Estimated household income from harvested crops							$\sum((Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i}))$

Appendix 2: Computation of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies

HHH Other sources of income frequencies

Step 1: Obtain frequencies for the ranks (from respondents)

	Santo Antao					Maio				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Ranks										
	Frequencies					Frequencies				
Sale of labour	8	1	0	2	0	3	-	-	-	-
Charcoal production	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
Petty trading/food vending	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Food processing	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salary	2	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
Pension	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Step 2: Compute total weighted scores and % weighted scores

Non-agric sources of income	Santo Antao							Maio						
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total weighted score	% Weighted score	1	2	3	4	5	Total weighted score	% Weighted score
Sale of labour	40	4	0	0	0	44	44.0	15	0	0	0	0	15	50.0
Petty trading/food vending	15	0	0	0	0	15	15.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Food processing	15	0	0	0	0	15	15.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Salary	10	0	0	0	0	10	10.0	0	10	0	0	0	10	33.0
Pension	5	0	0	0	0	5	5.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Charcoal production	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0	5	0	0	0	5	17.0
Other	0	12	0	0	0	12	12.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
						100	100.0						30	100.0

Appendix 3 - Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies – Household head expenditure in 12 months

Expenditure in 2022	Santo Antao							Maio						
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total weighted Score (A)	% Weighted score (B)	1	2	3	4	5	A	B
Food grain	60	0	0	0	0	60	25	25	4	0	0	0	29	17
Farm inputs	5	12	3	2	0	22	9	5	8	6	8	0	27	15
Livestock inputs	10	0	3	0	0	13	6	5	0	3	2	3	13	7
Labour/animal/tractor hire	35	4	3	2	0	34	19	5	4	0	0	0	9	5
Irrigation water charges	5	16	0	0	0	21	9	0	12	6	2	0	20	11
School expenses	10	4	0	2	1	17	7	0	8	0	0	1	9	5
Soup ingredients	0	8	3	0	0	11	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat and dairy	0	8	6	0	0	14	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Transportation (general)	0	4	3	0	1	8	3	5	0	0	0	0	5	3
Clothing	0	4	3	2	0	9	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amenities	0	0	3	2	1	6	3	30	8	3	2	0	43	25
Transportation (farm activities)	0	0	3	0	0	3	1	0	0	3	0	0	3	2
Orthodox health care for HHH	0	0	0	4	0	4	2	0	4	3	0	0	7	4
Traditional health care for HH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	6	3
Other specify	0	4	0	0	0	4	2	0	4	0	0	0	4	2